

CoP's architecture and stakeholder mapping for each Living Lab

Deliverable 1.1

CoP's architecture and stakeholder mapping for each Living Lab

D1.1: CoP's architecture and stakeholder mapping for each Living Lab

Summary

This deliverable introduces two of WP1's collaborative tools: Communities of Practice (CoP) and the Innovation Alliance (InAll). Chapters 2 and 3 are dedicated to the CoP and include the roadmap for CoP implementation in all Living Labs (e.g., meeting planning, preparation and facilitation, community planning, roles of the Coordinator and the Moderator, evaluation framework and cross-fertilisation), stakeholder mapping for the six Living Labs and the ethical issues and procedures to be considered in CoP implementation. Chapter 4 presents the framework for implementing the BWS Innovation Alliance, in particular the definition of the concept, the objectives behind it, the Consortium's experience to date in working with InAll, and the guidelines for implementation. The annexes provide practical information for CoP management, such as engagement tools for online meetings, moderation techniques organised by meeting elements and/or activities, a protocol for CoP Coordinators to follow when conducting the meetings, a template for reporting on CoP meetings, the CoP evaluation form and consent forms to be used in CoP operations.

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Table of contents

List of Figures.....	IV
List of Tables	V
List of Acronyms and Abbreviations	VI
Executive summary.....	I
Acknowledgments.....	1
1 Introduction	1
1.1 Objectives	1
1.2 Structure	1
2 Communities of Practice (CoP) in B-Water Smart.....	3
2.1 Communities of practice in research and innovation projects	3
2.2 Definition and Characteristics of Communities of Practice	3
2.3 CoP Roadmap in B-WaterSmart.....	6
2.3.1 First CoP Meeting Template.....	8
2.3.2 Template for in-between CoP Meetings / Focus Group Meetings	8
2.3.3 Last CoP Meeting Template	9
2.3.4 CoP Meeting Roadmap Infographic	9
2.4 Planning the Community.....	10
2.4.1 Select CoP Coordinator and CoP Moderator	10
2.4.2 Identify CoP Participants: Stakeholder Mapping and Selection	11
2.4.3 Stakeholder mapping for BWS Living Labs	16
2.5 Prepare and facilitate the CoP meetings	19
2.5.1 How to plan the meeting(s).....	19
2.6 After each CoP meeting and yearly	24
2.6.1 Responsibilities of the Moderators / Coordinators.....	24
2.7 Successful Meetings: Checklist for CoP Coordinators and Moderators.....	25
2.8 Evaluation of the CoP: rationale and approach	26
2.9 Cross-Fertilisation CoP	27
3 Ethical issues and procedures for the CoP.....	29
3.1 Handling of personal data	29
3.2 Stakeholder mapping: diversity and inclusion	30
3.3 CoP meetings and data collection	31
3.4 Non-EU countries.....	32
4 B-WaterSmart Innovation Alliance	33
4.1 What is BWS innovation alliance and what are its main objectives?	33
4.2 What is the consortium's past experience in similar innovation alliances?	35

4.3	Planning of InAll implementation	36
4.3.1	InAll roles	36
4.3.2	Common phased schedule	37
4.3.3	InAll work program.....	38
5	References	41
	Annex 1: Engagement tools for on-line meetings	43
	Annex 2: Moderation techniques.....	64
	Moderation techniques for introduction.....	66
	Moderation techniques to energise.....	74
	Moderation techniques for setting the scene	77
	Moderation techniques for defining the scope and direction	87
	Moderation techniques for brainstorming	90
	Moderation techniques for making knowledge explicit	95
	Moderation techniques for decision making	97
	Annex 3: Stakeholder distribution by type and role/profile per LL.....	101
	Annex 4: Template for Stakeholder Mapping	104
	Annex 5: Evaluation form	105
	Annex 6: Template for CoP meeting reporting.....	107
	Annex 7: Suggestions for designing a Protocol for CoP operation	109
	Annex 8: Consent forms	116

List of Figures

Figure 1: CoP Meeting Roadmap Infographic.....	10
Figure 2: Degrees of Participation (Koti et al., 2017)	13
Figure 3: Process for stakeholder engagement	16
Figure 4: CoP evaluation: conceptual framework (Source: Fulgenzi et al., 2020).....	27
Figure 5: R&D&I areas: Peer-to-peer Innovation Alliances with water utilities	36
Figure 2: Five-phased schedule for implementing BWS InAll.....	38
Figure 8 Decision tree for moderation techniques	65

List of Tables

Table 1: The characteristics of Communities of Practice	4
Table 2: First CoP Meeting Template.....	8
Table 3: In-between CoP Meetings Template.....	8
Table 4: In-between Focus Group Meetings Template	9
Table 5: Last CoP Meeting Template.....	9
Table 6: Value Matrix - Benefits to institutions and community members	15
Table 7: Classification criteria and categories for stakeholder mapping exercise	16
Table 8: Description of the stakeholders’ “role/profile”	17
Table 9: Distribution of the stakeholders by type and role/profile, per LL	17
Table 10: Timeline for stakeholder analysis and engagement.....	19
Table 11: Guidance on activities and elements to include in the first CoP meeting	21
Table 12: Guidance on activities and elements to include in the in-between CoP meetings	23
Table 13: Guidance on activities and elements to include in the last CoP meeting	23

List of Acronyms and Abbreviations

BINGO	Bringing INnovation to onGOing water management - a better future under Climate Change (H2020 funded project)
BWS	B-WaterSmart (H2020 funded project)
CoP	Community of Practice
CoP-SLO	Communities of Practice social learning outcomes
FG	Focus Groups
GA	Grant Agreement
KWR	KWR WATER B.V.
LL	Living Labs
LNEC	Laboratorio Nacional de Engenharia Civil
M	Month
MS	Milestone
NextGen	Towards a next generation of water systems and services for the circular economy (H2020 funded project)
STOP-IT	Strategic, Tactical, Operational Protection of water Infrastructure against cyber-physical Threats (H2020 funded project)
T	Task
WaterMining	Next generation water-smart management systems: large scale demonstrations for a circular economy and society (H2020 funded project)
WP	Work Package

Executive summary

Water is one of the world's most pressing and multifaceted issues. Innovative solutions (e.g., use of alternative water resources, industrial and urban water reuse, improved balance of water-energy-nutrients and increased efficiency in the water sector, selection, co-development and application of interlinked cost-effective technologies, concepts, water-smart data solutions) will come about as a result of effective collaboration, communication and knowledge exchange. Alongside the need to find these innovative solutions, research has shown that bringing together people from different backgrounds and interests can increase the potential for relevant innovations that can be effectively applied at the local level, as well as scaled up and disseminated.

B-WaterSmart aims to develop sustainable and economically efficient solutions for optimised water use to enable water-smart economies and societies in six European coastal cities and regions acting as Living Labs (LL) - Alicante, Bodø, Flanders, Lisbon, East Frisia and Venice - and supported by Communities of Practise (CoP) and an Innovation Alliance (InAll). CoP will bring together relevant key actors/stakeholders to ensure co-development, acceptance, implementation and thus actual systemic innovation in an interdisciplinary approach. In a nutshell, CoP will promote mutual learning and incorporate stakeholder knowledge, recognise commonalities and gaps between LLs while ensuring solution transferability and replicability, and analyse barriers and drivers to innovation growth and market outreach. InAll will implement peer-to-peer capacity building by testing and refining the water smartness assessment framework and demonstrate its usability as key for strategic planning towards greater water smartness.

The main objectives of WP1 - Co-create & demonstrate systemic innovation in six Living Labs - are to design and organize B-WaterSmart collaborative work (T1.1), implement and operate the Communities of Practice (T1.2), conduct the training actions on BWS products (T1.3), facilitate capacity building through an innovation alliance (T1.4) and manage systemic innovation in the BWS living labs, through the definition of tailored strategic agendas, and contribute to the vision of water smartness in the context of society and circular economy (T1.5). In this respect, WP1 will be the basis for the B-WaterSmart collaborative work, operationalised through several instruments that coordinate and complement each other and collectively aim to maximise the medium and long-term impacts of B-WaterSmart within its ecosystem:

- 6 Communities of practice (**CoP**; local, all local relevant stakeholders);
- 6 LL **strategic agendas** - implementation & management (local, all LL partners);
- 30+ **short courses** on BWS products and selected topics of common interest (global, all partners & CoP stakeholders);
- 1 **Innovation Alliance** across the 6 LLs on the water smartness assessment framework and its application (global, 6 LL owners + 6 LL mentors).

This deliverable presents the objectives and architecture of two of these instruments: Communities of Practice (chapters 2 and 3) and Innovation Alliance (chapter 4).”

Chapter 2 provides an overview of the role of CoP in research and innovation projects, the definition of the concept and its main features, the roadmap for BWS CoP, the planning of the community to be

involved, the preparation and facilitation of CoP meetings, the plan for actions to be undertaken after each CoP meeting and annually, the checklist for CoP coordinators and Moderators for successful meetings, the rationale and approach for CoP evaluation, and the importance of CoP for cross-fertilisation. The CoP roadmap gives a practical approach to planning CoP meetings, namely for planning the first CoP meeting, the meetings in between (CoP and focus groups) and the last CoP meeting, as well as provides a roadmap infographic. CoP planning includes the selection of the CoP Coordinator and Moderator and the identification of CoP participants. In this context, a stakeholder mapping for each Living Lab is presented that considers characterisation parameters such as "type of stakeholder" (e.g., regulators, utilities, trade associations, industry, etc.) and "role in the CoP" (e.g., "co-creators," "collaborators," "replicators," etc.). Preparing and Facilitating CoP Meetings provides practical steps to follow and a list of key elements and activities to include in the agenda for the first CoP meeting (annexes 1 and 2), actions required after each CoP meeting and annually, and the checklist for CoP coordinators and facilitators to conduct successful meetings, namely CoP meeting reporting, how to maintain stakeholders' interest between meetings and information sharing. Framed by Fulgenzi et al. (2019), six key success factors were identified, operationalised through indicators, and transformed into questions that can be used to assess CoP outcomes (as shown in Annex 5). To enhance and re-enforce mutual learning between the CoP organisers and stakeholders, cross-fertilisation or cross-learning meetings should take place throughout the project duration to add value to the overall CoP by bridging the gaps across topics, networking, and innovation potential. Chapter 3 underlines the ethical issues and procedures required for the planning and operation of the CoP, namely the handling of personal data and data collection before and during CoP meetings (annexes 7 and 8) and highlights the consideration of diversity and inclusion in stakeholder mapping.

Finally, Chapter 4 starts by introducing the concept underlying B-WaterSmart Innovation Alliance, the objectives behind it, the main differences with other WP1 collaborative instruments (e.g., CoP), and the consortium's previous experiences in similar innovation alliances. The planning of the InAll implementation presents the description of the roles of the key-actors in InAll (Task leader, LL owners and LL mentors), a common five-phased schedule and the InAll work program description for each implementation phase.

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1 Introduction

1.1 Objectives

The main objectives of WP1 are to design and organize B-WaterSmart (BWS) collaborative work (T1.1), implement and operate the CoP in six living labs (LL) (T1.2), conduct the training actions on BWS products (T1.3), facilitate capacity building through an innovation alliance (T1.4) and manage systemic innovation in the BWS Living Labs, through the definition of tailored strategic agendas, and contributing to the vision of water smartness in the context of society and the circular economy.

In this regard, WP1 will be the foundation of BWS **collaborative work**. The BWS systemic innovation approach goes far beyond the production of water smart methodologies and technologies as it builds on collaborative work with key stakeholders from different activity sectors and knowledge areas, on the development of solutions to societal, regulatory and governance issues, supporting methodologies to enable systematic and strategic planning towards systemic innovation for water-smartness, and capacity building.

Hence, WP1 will be operationalized via:

- 6 communities of practice (**CoP**; local, all local relevant stakeholders);
- 6 LL **strategic agendas** - implementation & management (local, all Living Lab partners);
- 30+ **short courses** on BWS products and selected topics of common interest (global, all partners & CoP stakeholders);
- 1 **Innovation Alliance** across the 6 LLs on the water smartness assessment framework and its application (global, 6 Living Lab owners + 6 Living Lab mentors).

These instruments are coordinated and complement each other, jointly aiming at maximizing the medium- and long-term impact of B-WaterSmart within its ecosystem.

Specifically, Task 1.1 was designed to provide and implement the structure and methodology of the remaining tasks within WP1 (T1.2 to T1.5), based on the inputs from T2.7, T3.1, T4.1 and T5.1. This task includes i) stakeholder mapping for each CoP based on the terms of reference given from WP5, ii) the definition of practices, methodologies, and tools to meet the objectives defined for the B-WaterSmart CoP operation, together with the timeline definition for the implementation, iii) setting up the innovation alliance (InAll) and defining its main objectives (T1.4), and iv) triggering the definition of the strategic agendas in the LLs.

This deliverable focuses on two of these instruments: Communities of Practice (chapters 1 to 3) and BWS Innovation Alliance (chapter 4).

1.2 Structure

The first two chapters provide guidance on implementing a roadmap for B-WaterSmart CoP and were mainly developed by the KWR research team, in a close collaboration with LNEC's WP1 team. The CoP Roadmap covers the planning, preparation, facilitation, and implementation of the CoP meetings, as well as outlining the evaluation framework that will guide the assessment of the added value of the CoP. Chapter two also includes a section on stakeholder mapping in each Living Lab and a section on how to implement cross-fertilisation between the six local CoP. The ICS-UL team was responsible

for chapter three, which presents the guidelines and ethical rules to be followed in the WP1 collaborative work, as well as the necessary materials (protocol for CoP operation and consent forms), with special attention to CoP and FG operation. Finally, chapter four presents the outline of the B-WaterSmart Innovation Alliance (InAll), especially the definition of the concept, the objectives behind it, and the guidelines for its implementation and was the responsibility of the WP1 lead partner. In general, the Annexes provide practical information to be used in CoP, such as engagement tools for online meetings, moderation techniques categorised by meeting elements and/or activities in sequential order (i.e., introduction, setting the scene, defining scope and direction, brainstorming, making knowledge explicit, and decision making), an evaluation form and a template for reporting on CoP meetings, and a suggested protocol for CoP Coordinators to follow for running CoP. The annexes also include a template for LL owners to proceed with stakeholder analysis and a consent form to be used in CoP operations.

2 Communities of Practice (CoP) in B-Water Smart

“Communities of practice, defined as social learning systems that bring together people who share a concern or a passion for something they do and learn how to do it better as they interact regularly” (Wenger-Trayner & Wenger-Trayner, 2015)

2.1 Communities of practice in research and innovation projects

Innovative solutions to the world’s most pressing issues will come about as a result of effective collaboration, communication and knowledge exchange. Research has shown that bringing together people from different backgrounds and with different interests can increase the potential for relevant innovations that can be effectively applied at the local level as well as scaled up and disseminated. Therefore, Communities of Practice are a vital component to EU Projects, such as B-Water Smart (BWS) to deliver solutions tailored and co-created by a diverse group of people that can ensure the long-term success of technologies and innovations developed and tested in the project Living Labs.

Within B-WaterSmart, KWR, as T1.2 leader, will help CoP facilitators and moderators (see section 2.4.1) to design and implement CoP to engage locally relevant stakeholders from various expertise and backgrounds. Each CoP will enable the participants to discuss, work together and outline the steps towards successful design and implementation of water-related technologies and innovative solutions. Furthermore, participants in the CoP will benefit from learning from each other and developing relationships with local partners on tangible technologies and innovations for a water-wise world.

At each step of the way, KWR researchers will support the CoP facilitators and moderators to deliver effective CoP meetings, both online and in person, with the latest tools and techniques. KRW researchers can also offer training to those who feel in need of additional support with the engagement and moderation techniques outlined in this Deliverable (see Annex 1: Engagement tools for on-line meetings and Annex 2: Moderation techniques).

This guidance is intended for the use by CoP facilitators, support partners and moderators. It builds on previous work conducted in several EU projects where CoP were implemented (BINGO, STOP-IT, NextGen and WaterMining), as well as in existing literature. The document is a practical piece to be applied by LL owners and leaders, as well as innovative, with a multitude of approaches and avenues to convene multidisciplinary CoP meetings.

2.2 Definition and Characteristics of Communities of Practice

The construction of the concept of CoP is structured on the basis of learning and its dimensions and can be seen as a social learning system. CoP are formed by people who voluntarily share the same interest or passion, interact regularly, exchange information and knowledge, seek to sustain the community and share learning, so that they can be characterized as having the following dimensions: joint venture, mutual involvement, and shared repertoire. Social scientists have used versions of the concept of community of practice for a variety of purposes and applications, although the origin and use of the concept is anchored in learning theory (Wenger, 2010).

What is a Community of Practice?

“Communities of practice (CoPs) are defined as social learning systems that bring together people who share a concern or a passion for something they do and learn how to do it better as they interact regularly” (Wenger-Trayner & Wenger-Trayner, 2015, in Fulgenzi et al., 2020).

Table 1: The characteristics of Communities of Practice

Key characteristics of a community of practice	
1.	Sustained mutual relationships – harmonious or conflictual
2.	Shared ways of engaging in doing things together
3.	The rapid flow of information and propagation of innovation
4.	Absence of introductory preambles, as if conversations and interactions were merely the continuation of an ongoing process
5.	Very quick setup of a problem to be discussed
6.	Substantial overlap in participants' descriptions of who belongs to the community
7.	Knowing what others know, what they can do, and how they can contribute to an enterprise
8.	Mutually defining participants identities
9.	The ability to assess the appropriateness of actions and products
10.	Specific tools, representations, and other artifacts
11.	Local lore, shared stories, inside jokes, knowing laughter
12.	Jargon and shortcuts to communication as well as the ease of producing new ones
13.	Certain styles recognized as displaying membership
14.	A shared discourse reflecting a certain perspective on the world

Source: Cox, 2005

There are three fundamental elements to a CoP: the domain, the community and the practice. To cultivate a CoP, the combination of the three must be developed in parallel (Wenger-Trayner & Wenger-Trayner, 2015):

Three Fundamental Elements of a CoP

Domain:

A CoP distinguishes from other networks since its members identify themselves by a shared domain of interest. Membership involves a commitment to the domain and a shared competence.

Community:

While showing their interest in their domain, community members share information, help each other and join activities and discussions. In this form of interaction, members build relationships in order to learn from each other and to support each other.

Practice:

Members of a CoP do not only share a common interest, they are engaged in common practice, as an iterative social process, where they develop a shared repertoire of resources. These can be experiences, stories, tools or ways of addressing recurring problems. To develop this kind of a shared practice it takes time and continuous interaction.

As such, CoP bring together relevant stakeholders to develop a common understanding of a given topic, to arrive at solutions that are co-developed, supported, and finally accepted by all parties. A CoP can evolve naturally due to the members' common interest in a specific field, or it can be created deliberately with the goal of gaining knowledge related to a particular domain. When applied intentionally as a learning concept, the overall goal of a CoP is to maintain the already existing knowledge about a specific topic and use it to create new ideas through an ongoing exchange of information (Koti et al., 2017). The interaction among different actors seems to improve the decision-making process at the individual, societal and institutional level mostly when there is a strong investment on working based on a shared vision (Freitas et al., 2018).

In ensuring the viability of CoP, it will be important to remember that they are made of **people**. As a result, people need to feel that the following elements are available within the CoP to motivate them to join, contribute, engage, share and learn. Key elements to bring into CoP for their effective implementation include enabling a sense of belonging, respect, diversity, flexibility, motivation, and trust. From the beginning, CoP need to follow bottom-up approaches that enable each stakeholder to take part in the formulation of their safe space for knowledge sharing, learning and exchange.

2.3 CoP Roadmap in B-WaterSmart

This section provides practical guidance on how to organise and structure the CoP Meeting Roadmap for each Living Lab in the B-WaterSmart project and includes a general indication of the content of the meetings to be held throughout the project duration, with tips and suggestions, and also an infographic to be populated for ease of understanding by LL owners, WP leaders and project partners. The meetings planned under CoP refer to the regular meetings of the CoP, which are more focused on discussing and validating the strategic goals and agendas of LL towards water smartness long term visions, while the focus group meetings will be more dedicated to discussing specific topics identified as priorities by the LL owners (e.g., water reuse, mineral and nutrient recovery, regulatory framework, policy and governance drivers and barriers, social acceptance of BWS solutions).

Templates are provided for LL Owners, CoP Coordinators and Moderators to fill out in order to start planning the CoP Meetings, to be later validated by the stakeholders engaged for the CoP. While filling out the templates below, keep in mind the planning processes noted in Sections 2.4 (Planning the Community) and 2.5 (Prepare and Facilitate CoP Meetings) of this document.

A CoP Roadmap includes:

1. definition of the scope of the CoP and focus group meetings;
2. definition of the topic of each of the meeting;
3. identification of the type of meeting (entire community or a subset in focus groups);
4. identification of the stakeholders to join the meetings;
5. timeline of the meetings.

The template tables below comprise the minimum information to include in the roadmap. Tables may be expanded, and more rows added as needed. For example, if you want to use this template as a starting point to prepare your CoP meetings, you can add a row including Methods to use in the meeting (moderation techniques, engagement tools, etc.), and so forth.

In general, at least four CoP meetings should be held throughout the duration of the B-WaterSmart project (i.e., one per year), with the participation of all identified CoP stakeholders (the entire community). There is the possibility to plan for more CoP Meetings as needed, either with the entire community or with a subset of the community in “Focus Groups” meetings, depending on the topic to be discussed in further detail. The CoP meetings should address cross-cutting issues (e.g., LL’s Strategic Agendas) (Schmuck et al., 2021), whereas a focus group meeting could address a specific topic with a smaller group of interested individuals from the general stakeholder map (e.g., regulatory issues, water reuse). In this sense, it is expected that the first and last CoP meetings will be dedicated to the discussion and validation of the strategic agendas towards water smartness in the Living Labs, whereas the in-between meetings, as well as the focus groups, will address topics previously identified as key areas (e.g., energy production and recovery, nutrient and mineral recovery for agriculture, industrial symbiosis, urban planning and green areas, and environment and ecosystems). The stabilisation of the topics of each meeting will take place in the following months before the first CoP meeting to occur (see Table 10).

Having a roadmap is vital to help planning the CoP activities according to what needs to be shared/discussed with stakeholders, as well as to allocate adequate time to plan the CoP meetings, especially on-line meetings, which are recognised as being very time-consuming.

Checklist for filling out CoP Roadmap Templates

1. First, Living Lab mentors and owners should discuss internally and fill in as many of the template tables below as needed.
 - a. Discuss among LL partners the scope of your CoP: think of your stakeholders and their concerns and interests, think of cross-cutting issues to focus on for each meeting); below some examples of cross cutting issues are presented:
 - i. legal aspects: legal/regulatory barriers and opportunities (EU and national regulations) e.g., for water reuse or recovered material use;
 - ii. social perception and barriers for the use of recovered materials and water;
 - iii. requirements (e.g., quality) for the use/reuse of products (water, recovered material): e.g., water reuse technology: for what purpose? Depending on the purpose, which water quality requirements are needed?
 - iv. market for the products of the project.
2. Once the scope of the CoP is identified, it is important to narrow it down to a number of specific topics to be discussed with the CoP stakeholders.
3. Depending on the topics and whether they need to be discussed with the entire CoP community or with a subset of individuals from the community, it will be necessary to define how many CoP and focus groups (FG) meetings are needed throughout the project; please consider a minimum of four CoP meetings with the entire community, i.e., one per year to keep continuity of the stakeholder engagement.
4. Then share the pre-filled tables with the WP leaders and LL Coordinators to ask them to contribute with the related WP/Living Labs contents to the different meetings. WP and LL certainly have issues they would like to discuss with CoP stakeholders. For this particular issue, please keep in mind MS05 – Information needs from CoP (Wencki et al., 2021). Some of these issues have already been identified in the project proposal, but others may become clear now that WP have started to work. Knowing how and when CoP will engage with WP is important for both WP and Living Labs, so as to plan accordingly.
5. Fill in the infographic below once you have identified the number, tentative date of the meetings and topics.
6. Validate the planning of the CoP roadmap with all stakeholders at the 1st CoP meeting and fill in the templates below as much as possible prior to that meeting.
7. Place the finalised document with tables and infographic in the online shared space accessible to all Living Labs and project partners (e.g., BWS nextcloud drive).

The tables presented in the next following sub-sections describe the structure to be adopted to the definition of all CoP meetings across all BWS Living Labs. The content varies in function of four different parameters, namely: a) planning the meeting; b) selecting participants, c) defining the objectives of each meeting, and d) identifying the contribution of/for specific WPs.

2.3.1 First CoP Meeting Template

Table 2: First CoP Meeting Template

CoP #1	“Setting the Scene” (Or choose another title as you see fit for the first meeting)
Planning	Month (<i>tentative – indicate in project month number and actual month and year</i>)
Participants	All stakeholders identified in stakeholder mapping and involved in the LL.
Objective(s) of the meeting	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. Validate with stakeholders pre-identified objectives, mission and scope of CoP 2. Validate with stakeholders the composition of the community and fill any gaps (are we missing any important stakeholder?) 3. Co-define with stakeholders short and long-term value and impact of CoP. 4. Co-define with stakeholders the specific ways the CoP will operate, namely, decision-making procedures, communication strategy in between meetings, activities for the community in between meetings, responsibilities of members, contact person(s), etc. 5. Other as needed. <p>See Section 2.6.1.1 for more details.</p>
Related WP	Indicate which WPs/ Living Labs will add content to this meeting. Also indicate what content the WPs/Living Labs will add.

2.3.2 Template for in-between CoP Meetings / Focus Group Meetings

Table 3: In-between CoP Meetings Template

CoP #2, #3... (in-between meetings)	Topic (define the topics for the subsequent CoP meetings)
Planning	Month (<i>tentative – indicate in project month number and actual month and year</i>)
Participants	All stakeholders identified in stakeholder mapping and involved in the LL, and any new ones identified in the 1st CoP meeting. Any invited guest as needed (e.g., stakeholders potentially interested in the products of the project, for transferability).
Objective(s) of the meeting	Indicate to the best of your knowledge now the possible objectives for the subsequent CoP meetings.
Related WP	Indicate which WPs/ Living Labs will add content to this meeting. Also indicate what content the WP/Living Labs will add.

Table 4: In-between Focus Group Meetings Template

Focus Group (FG) Meetings (identify the FG as A, B, C, etc)	Topic (define the topics for the subsequent FG meetings)
Planning	Month (<i>tentative – indicate in project month number and actual month and year</i>)
Participants	Subset of stakeholders from the CoP community, as needed, based on the topic selected for the FG meeting. You may want to keep the meeting open to also the other CoP members even if it is not their topic of expertise. Any invited guest as needed (e.g., stakeholders potentially interested in the products of the project, for transferability).
Objective(s) of the meeting	Indicate to the best of your knowledge now the possible objectives for a focus group meeting.
Related WP	Indicate which WPs/ Living Labs will add content to this meeting. Also indicate what content the WP/Living Labs will add.

2.3.3 Last CoP Meeting Template

Table 5: Last CoP Meeting Template

CoP #4 (last)	Final deliberations and next steps
Planning	Month (<i>tentative – indicate in project month number and actual month and year</i>)
Participants	All stakeholders identified in stakeholder mapping and involved in the LL, and any new ones identified in the 1st CoP meeting. Any invited guest as needed (e.g., stakeholders potentially interested in the products of the project, for transferability).
Objective(s) of the meeting	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. Last resolutions. 2. Future of CoP/outputs – beyond the project. 3. Other as needed.
Related WP	Indicate which WPs/ Living Labs will add content to this meeting. Please also indicate what content the WP/Living Labs will add.

2.3.4 CoP Meeting Roadmap Infographic

Figure 1 presents a suggested roadmap that can be adapted to as many CoP and focus group meetings as needed for the BWS Living Labs.

Figure 1: CoP Meeting Roadmap Infographic

2.4 Planning the Community

Before launching a CoP, the Coordinator, Moderator, and participants have to be selected. The following sections explain each step of the planning in detail and chronological order.

2.4.1 Select CoP Coordinator and CoP Moderator

One of the most important roles in a CoP is the role of the **CoP Coordinator**. The Coordinator is in charge of establishing and managing the CoP, including setting up the community, maintaining stakeholder engagement throughout the relationship-building project, helping members focus on the domain and developing the practice. More specifically, the CoP Coordinator is responsible for organising, preparing for, and facilitating CoP meetings (Brouwer et al., 2018), as well as ensuring that information from the project and Living Labs is shared with the moderator and CoP stakeholders.

The CoP Coordinator is the official contact person for the CoP and is responsible for selecting a CoP moderator and stakeholders (section 2.4.1). The CoP Coordinator should remain as the same person over the course of the project.

The **CoP Moderator** also fulfils an important role within the CoP and is selected before the

first CoP meeting. The role of CoP Moderator is to support the CoP Coordinator in delivering the CoP meetings. The CoP Coordinator can fulfil both roles, but it is recommended to have both a Coordinator and a Moderator, and the roles and responsibilities for both should be clearly established before the first meeting. The CoP moderator is in charge of running the CoP meetings, moderating the meetings,

Coordinator & Moderator Checklist

Coordinator

- Select CoP Moderator
- Select CoP stakeholders
- Build relationships
- Share information
- Official contact person

Moderator

- Support CoP Coordinator
- Organise & deliver meetings
- Provide safe environment
- Encourage active engagement

and has to provide the structure (rules) to have a creative and safe environment for the CoP participants to collaborate and exchange knowledge (Brouwer et al., 2018). The CoP moderator should remain the same person over the course of the project.

In case the Coordinator or Moderator cannot remain the same throughout the duration of the project (although this is not recommended), the following hand-over elements apply: 1) inform the project Coordinator (e.g., IWW) of the leaving one/two months in advance; 2) inform the CoP Coordinator and/or Moderator if they remain in the role; 3) find a suitable new Moderator or Coordinator who can fulfill the responsibilities until the end of the project.

Organisation Support

The **Work Package leader** and/or **KWR** can support you with training on moderation techniques, online tools, and provide support to organise the meetings etc.

2.4.2 Identify CoP Participants: Stakeholder Mapping and Selection

Based on the ambitions set for the CoP, relevant stakeholders are invited to become a member (Brouwer et al., 2018). Therefore, elements and activities within the CoP should be designed as catalysts for a community's natural evolution. Since CoP usually build on preexisting personal networks, it is the CoP Coordinator and Moderator's task to help the community develop and grow through physical, social and organisational structures (Koti et al., 2017).

2.4.2.1 Criteria for stakeholders' identification & mapping of relationships

Start with identifying the organisations and then the specific person in the organisation to approach. Start with people in your network but be aware that the people you know may not be the right people to join the CoP, although they may be able to help you select the right people. Furthermore, clearly address whether the general public is going to be involved or not: we strongly recommend keeping CoP only for experts, and to engage with the public in different ways, unless those convened to the CoP may be representative of citizens' organisations.

There are important questions to ask and considerations to make before proceeding with stakeholder mapping to gain an understanding about the stakeholders, their interest and power dynamics within the CoP. The outline below details these issues/considerations.

1. Which organisation should be invited?
2. Who are the key stakeholders/individuals in the organisation?
3. What is the professional experience and position in the organisation of the attendees?
4. What is the relationship of the organisation and/or individual stakeholders with other stakeholders/organisations? (i.e., consider power relations and dynamics).
 - a. Consider the stakeholders' position within the context of B-WaterSmart and their interest and influence in the specific LL or technology.
 - b. Consider also involving people with different levels of expertise within the same organisation, i.e., strategic and operational level. In order to determine which level of expertise is needed, reflect on the scope and objectives of the CoP. If both strategic and operational level stakeholders from one organisation within the CoP are needed, reflect on whether both could speak freely if attending the same meeting. These are important considerations in selecting and facilitating stakeholders within a CoP.
5. Relation of the organisation to the water sector (i.e., are they linked to water sector, or indirectly involved, if so, in what way?).
6. Known enthusiasm, interest and knowledge of the invited person with regards to the mission of the project and the CoP.
7. In order to build a solid member base, it is important to reach out to members that cover all aspects of the stakeholders' community stakeholders. Diversity is needed both in background, ethnicity, gender/age, professional maturity and spatial scope of action (local, regional, national) (Freitas et al., 2018).
8. Make a list of the potential stakeholders, in manageable numbers, to reach out to and track your email outreach to them and their responses.
9. Finally, gather ideas about your stakeholders and **map relationships** between them (positive, neutral, and negative) aligned with their interest and power dynamics. Note down some foreseeable successes and challenges for the CoP based on the stakeholders and prepare for the first meeting by outlining these challenges and potential barriers clearly. In this regard, also consider the guidelines for the stakeholders mapping in section 3.B-WaterSmart: Guidelines for CoP and the LLs and in Annex 7.A of MS3 - Guidelines to operate LLs and CoP (Gomes et al., 2021).

Who are the potential stakeholders?

Organisations

- Linked sectors (construction, agriculture, transport, food industry, energy)
- Regulators
- End-Users
- Technology Providers
- Industry
- Municipalities
- Consultancies
- Waterboard or utility

Individuals

- Engineers
- Architects
- Urban Planners
- Natural Scientists
- Social scientists
- Policy-Makers
- Leaders and heads of organisations
- Operational staff
- Researchers
- Junior experts
- Data Scientists
- Local experts
- Living lab actors

Tip !

Once all stakeholders have accepted to join the CoP, be sure to keep and manage a separate list of the stakeholders, including information such as: contact details, role, organisation, interest, contribution (material, data, facilities), their expectations, meeting attendance, for your own records as contact information of the stakeholders cannot be shared.

2.4.2.2 Important considerations in stakeholder selection and involvement

The stakeholders participating in the meetings ought to remain the same throughout the entire lifespan of the CoP (Brouwer et al., 2018). However, external experts may be invited occasionally to CoP meetings as desired by the stakeholders, supported by the Living Labs, CoP Coordinators and moderators. Therefore, it is essential to understand that different stakeholders will speak different “languages” (i.e., scientists vs. practitioners) and it is decisive to ensure an effective communication and knowledge understanding among the stakeholders in CoP/FG meetings.

Also note that different stakeholders within the CoP will have different involvement levels or participation degrees. CoP consist of three main levels of community participation: the core group, the active group, and the peripheral group (see Figure 2). The core group (usually 10 to max. 15 percent of all members) is the heart of the community, actively participating in discussions, taking on community projects, identifying topics for the community and moving the community along its learning agenda. This group takes on much of the community’s leadership and becomes auxiliary to the Coordinator. The level outside the core group is called the active group, it is also rather small and consists of 15 to 20 percent of the whole community. The active group members attend meetings regularly and participate occasionally in the community forums. The biggest group build the members of the peripheral level. They rarely participate. Instead, they remain peripheral and watch the interaction of the core and active members. Even though they seem to be passive their peripheral activities are an essential dimension of CoP. Hence, make sure that the active group is consisting of a broad number of stakeholders (Koti et al., 2017).

Figure 2: Degrees of Participation (Koti et al., 2017)

There is no ideal size or number of participants in CoP and determining who needs to be in the room is a joint decision by Living Labs, CoP Coordinators and stakeholders. Note, however, that a large

group will imply additional planning and coordination, potential complexities and will demand for a more experienced CoP facilitator.

2.4.2.3 Highlight the value of CoP to stakeholders

Demonstrating the added value of CoP to stakeholders is a crucial step in inviting them to join and ensuring their active involvement. There are several factors and specific LL elements that will attract stakeholders to a CoP. Consider mentioning in your invitation the following:

Another step to motivate the stakeholders to participate in the CoP can be done through the **Wow-How-Now elevator pitch approach**, which can be used in your initial email to the potential stakeholders, as well as through identifying the short and long-term values. The value matrix table below (Table 6) provides some examples of benefits for institutions and community members in general, but it is adaptable based on the CoP specific context and purposes and the stakeholders invited. This can be used to inform your Wow-How-Now elevator pitch.

WOW | Think of an intriguing opening statement to get attention

HOW | Explain briefly how your community addresses a need or solves a problem

NOW | Give an example: "Now..." or "For example..." of current actions or activities

Table 6: Value Matrix - Benefits to institutions and community members

	Short term value	Long-term value
	<i>Improve business outcome</i>	<i>Develop organisational capabilities</i>
Benefits to institutions	<p>Arena for problem solving. Quick answers to questions. Reduced time and costs. Improved quality of decisions. More perspectives on problems. Coordination, standardisation and synergies across stakeholders. Resources for implementing strategies. Strengthened quality assurance. Ability to take risk with backing of the community. Standardized messages.</p>	<p>Ability to execute a strategic plan Authority with clients. Increased retention of talent. Capacity for knowledge-development projects. Forum for “benchmarking” against rest of industry. Knowledge-based alliances. Emergence of unplanned capabilities Capacity to develop new strategic options. Ability to foresee technological developments. Ability to take advantage of emerging market opportunities.</p>
	<i>Improve experience of work</i>	<i>Foster professional development</i>
Benefits to community members	<p>Help with challenges. Access to expertise. Better able to contribute to team. Confidence in one’s approach to problems. Fun of being with colleagues. More meaningful participation. Sense of belonging. Trust in technology.</p>	<p>Forum for expanding skills and expertise. Network for keeping abreast of a field. Enhanced professional reputation. Increased marketability and employability. Strong sense of professional identity</p>

Source: Wenger et al., 2002

2.4.3 Stakeholder mapping for BWS Living Labs

2.4.3.1 Process of identification of stakeholders in each LL

As mentioned earlier, stakeholder mapping involves identifying and analysing the organisations and individuals that have an interest in the CoP objectives in order to effectively manage and initiate a successful communication and co-creation process.

Figure 3: Process for stakeholder engagement

Taking the steps described in section 2.4.2 as detailed guideline, the WP1 team started the stakeholder identification process by compiling an excel file with all the information on potential stakeholders provided by the LL owners and mentors during several moments of interaction, namely work meetings and joint workshops to define the strategic agendas for each LL, specific inputs on their work priorities and previous BWS Deliverables and Milestones (Amores et al., 2021; Delicado, 2021; Gomes et al., 2021; Schmuck et al., 2021; Wencki et al., 2021).

Built on this information, LL mentors and owners were asked to review and classify each previously identified stakeholder according to the guidelines provided in the stakeholder mapping template (Gomes et al., 2021) (see Annex A – MS3 Guidelines to operate LLs and CoP) based on two previously established criteria: 1) type of stakeholder and 2) profile/role each stakeholder may play in local CoP.

Table 7: Classification criteria and categories for stakeholder mapping exercise

Type of Stakeholder	Role/Profile
Government institution	Partner
Municipality	Core co-creator
Regional/Local authority (e.g., parish)	Follower
Service/Technology provider	Collaborator
Utilities (water, waste, wastewater, energy, multi-services)	Observer
Regulator	Other
Financial/funder	
Sectoral association	
Environmental NGO	
Local association	
Research/academia	
Industry	
Umbrella organisation	
Agriculture sector	
Water Board	
Other	

Table 8: Description of the stakeholders’ “role/profile”

Role/Profile	Description
Partner	This role/profile applies only to the partners officially involved in the B-WaterSmart Consortium, either as part of the Living Labs or as participants/leaders of the project’s work packages or as third parties (e.g., Lisboa E-Nova in Lisbon LL)
Core co-creator	Actors and organisations that are key to the development of the core topics of the local CoP and have a central role and/or influence at the local/regional or national level (e.g., water and agricultural sector organisations, industry, municipalities, regional/local authorities)
Follower	Actors and organisations within or outside the current geographical scope of LL who will participate in workshops or dissemination events to gain in-depth knowledge of BWS solutions and have the explicit intention to apply them in their respective sectors/intervention areas (e.g., municipalities, water utilities, companies, sectoral associations).
Collaborator	Actors and organisations that are core to the development of policies and decision-making processes related to the development of circular economy in the water sector. This category includes policymakers and decision-makers such as environmental authorities and regulators
Observer	Actors and organisations attending the CoP meetings or dissemination events that follow the co-creation process but do not actively participate in it

Table 9 shows the distribution of the 182 identified stakeholders by type and by role/profile. Although the list is not definitive, as changes from the original planning may occur during the analysis and engagement phase, it is recommended that CoP with a high number of stakeholders be aware that large groups are more difficult to manage. This can lead to a lower quality of expected outcomes for CoP if the dynamics of larger groups are not properly managed. It is therefore very important that LL secure a skilled moderator for the meetings.

Table 9: Distribution of the stakeholders by type and role/profile, per LL

LL	Type of Stakeholder	Partner	Core co-creator	Follower	Collaborator	Observer	Other	Total
Alicante	Government institution	0	0	0	0	2	0	2
	Municipality	0	0	0	1	0	0	1
	Regional /Local authority	0	1	0	0	0	0	1
	Service/Technology provider	1	0	0	1	0	0	2
	Utility (Water/multi-utility)	2	0	0	0	0	0	2
	Regulator/financial	0	0	0	2	0	0	2
	Sectoral association	0	0	0	0	2	0	2
	Local association	0	1	0	0	3	0	4
	Research/academia	2	0	0	0	0	0	2
	Industry	0	2	0	0	6	0	8
	Total	5	4	0	4	13	0	26
Bodø	Government institution	0	0	0	2	0	7	9
	Municipality	1	0	0	1	2	0	4
	Service/Technology provider	3	0	0	0	0	0	3
	Regulator	0	0	0	0	0	2	2
	Financial/funder	0	0	0	2	0	0	2
	Sectoral association	0	0	0	1	0	2	3
	Research/academia	2	0	0	0	0	0	2
	Utility (waste, energy)	0	0	0	2	0	0	2
		Total	6	0	0	8	2	11

LL	Type of Stakeholder	Partner	Core co-creator	Follower	Collaborator	Observer	Other	Total
East Frisia	Government institution	0	0	0	0	1	0	1
	Municipality	0	0	2	1	0	0	3
	Regional/Local authority	0	0	0	1	0	0	1
	Service/Technology provider	2	0	0	0	0	0	2
	Utility (water)	1	0	0	0	2	0	3
	Regulator	0	0	0	0	0	4	4
	Sectoral association	0	0	0	0	1	1	2
	Local association	0	0	0	0	1	0	1
	Research/academia	1	0	2	0	0	0	3
	Industry	0	0	0	0	1	0	1
	Umbrella organisation	0	0	3	0	0	0	3
	Total		4	0	7	2	6	5
Flanders	Service/Technology provider	1	0	0	1	1	0	3
	Utility (water)	1	0	0	1	0	0	2
	Research/academia	2	0	0	0	4	0	6
	Agriculture sector	0	0	0	0	3	0	3
	Total		4	0	0	2	8	0
Lisbon	Government institution	0	2	0	0	3	0	5
	Municipality	1	5	0	0	0	0	6
	Regional/Local authority	0	2	0	0	0	0	2
	Service/Technology provider	2	0	1	0	0	2	5
	Utility (water)	1	2	1	0	1	0	5
	Regulator	0	4	0	0	0	0	4
	Sectoral association	0	7	0	0	2	0	9
	Environmental NGO	0	1	0	0	3	0	4
	Research/academia	2	1	0	0	0	0	3
	Other	0	1	0	0	0	0	1
Total		6	25	2	0	9	2	44
Venice	Government institution	0	0	0	2	0	0	2
	Regional/Local authority	0	0	0	1	0	0	1
	Service/Technology provider	3	0	0	0	0	0	3
	Utility (water)	2	0	0	0	0	0	2
	Regulator	0	0	0	1	0	0	1
	Sectoral association	0	0	1	9	0	0	10
	Research/academia	1	0	0	2	0	0	3
	Industry	0	0	0	0	4	0	4
Total		6	0	1	15	4	0	26

2.4.3.2 Next steps until the start of the CoP

The next steps of stakeholder mapping comprise the analysis and engagement of the mapped stakeholders. The table below presents the timeline for those steps.

Table 10: Timeline for stakeholder analysis and engagement

Timeline	Stakeholder analysis and engagement
June – July 21	Define CoP Coordinators and Moderators/Facilitators.
	Consolidation of the stakeholder analysis, including sub-categories, target organisations, identification of stakeholder interests, needs, stakes, challenges, and risks.
	Collect and analyse information on stakeholders already identified regarding: a) Key functions; b) Interaction with other stakeholders; c) Degree of influence; d) Key interests and level of interest; e) Objectives for engaging in CoP. This information can be collected previously or during the first CoP meeting (see Annex 4: Template for Stakeholder Mapping).
	Organise the stakeholders' group regarding their involvement in CoP and/or Focus Groups meetings.
	Define the CoP timeline and engagement calendar.
	Define the topics for the CoP/FG meetings
Aug 21	Decide on the engagement tools and moderations techniques (see Annex 1: Engagement tools for on-line meetings and Annex 2: Moderation techniques).
Sep – Oct21	Conduct the first CoP meetings.

2.5 Prepare and facilitate the CoP meetings

CoP meetings should be designed in such way that participants are willing to collaborate, learn together and exchange knowledge. To create such conditions aimed at social learning (Medema et al., 2014) emphasize the importance of building trust and mutual understanding, facilitating ongoing reflection by embracing an intentional learning approach, and creating an enabling environment for informal and open discourse and dialogue (Brouwer et al., 2018).

2.5.1 How to plan the meeting(s)

Below are the steps that CoP Coordinator and/or Moderator should follow to plan the meetings:

1. CoP Coordinator and/or Moderator to pre-define the objectives and goals of each meeting together with relevant project partners.
2. Logistics (In-person or online)

- a. decide on the venue and facilities (location/online tool);
- b. organise the set-up (IT resources, etc.);
- c. invite the participants
- d. define a budget (if applicable).

Tip !

Stakeholders are spending their valuable time – make this time as comfortable as possible and provide a fruitful atmosphere with some snacks and soft drinks if appropriate. For online meetings, ensure multiple breaks and support is offered for technical difficulties.

3. Define the timing and an agenda for the meeting

- a. email all defined stakeholders to define a date using a polling tool (e.g., Doodle Poll);
- b. outline the agenda and timing for each activity within the meeting.

4. If the meeting is online, the duration of the meeting should not be too long (i.e., not exceeding 2-3 hours) and allow for breaks to allow the participants to refresh. Interaction in online meetings is especially important, considering the differences in attention of the participants as compared to an in-person meeting (see Annex 1: Engagement tools for on-line meetings and Annex 2: Moderation techniques). If the meeting is in person, it can be for slightly longer than an online meeting, also with breaks and interaction.

5. Design or adopt a Protocol for CoP operation to ensure a bottom-up approach and gain consensus on the community's approach (see Annex 7: Suggestions for designing a Protocol for CoP operation).

6. Prepare and provide any important information for the stakeholders to prepare for the meeting (i.e., information about the project, ensure consent forms are completed and signed before the meeting, rights to withdraw and anonymization procedures; see Annex 8: Consent forms).

7. Select moderation techniques and engagement tools: The following items are important considerations for each and every meeting. Specific moderation techniques and engagement tools are explained in detail in Annex 1: Engagement tools for on-line meetings and Annex 2: Moderation techniques. Although it has never been used by the KWR, the open-source tool DECIDIM + Big Blue Button (see Annex 1: Engagement tools for on-line meetings), developed by BWS partner ENGINEERING - INGEGNERIA INFORMATICA SPA (ENG), offers great potential for engagement in collaborative work in an online environment and for the application of moderation techniques during the CoP meetings. The tool is composed of two main modules: the first supports on-line participatory processes and the second runs on-line meetings (like zoom) with a whiteboard embedded. The deployment of the tool is also planned for each Living Lab and it will be possible to continue using this tool after the end of the project.

8. Following this section are subsections on specific activities and elements to include in the 1st CoP meeting and subsequent meetings:

1. deliver and transfer knowledge;
2. share experiences and co-produce knowledge;
3. co-create new ideas and innovations;
4. promote the long-term value of the CoP;
5. enable socialising and relationship building (informal or formal).

2.5.1.1 First Meeting with CoP Stakeholders

The key elements and activities that the first CoP meeting should consider in the agenda are presented below. The first meeting is vital to build a bottom-up approach, to meet the stakeholders and to co-define the objectives and ambitions of the CoP for the duration of the project.

Before the first CoP meeting, the CoP Coordinator and/or Moderator should **pre-define the objectives and goals**, which will then be validated by the participants during the meeting. In B-WaterSmart, the strategic agendas defined under Task 1.5 will probably be discussed and validated with stakeholders. In the preparation of 1st CoP meeting, CoP Coordinator and/or Moderator should also consider the following questions when defining the meeting goal and objectives:

- What is the ambition and goal of the CoP?
- What is the primary scope? (learning, support, communication)
- What is the value (benefits) it brings to its members? To the sector?
- What are the focus areas, key issues?

Table 11 below provides some guidance on the activities and elements to be included in the first meeting to set up successful CoP. The elements and activities are organised in chronological order and are vital aspects for the effective set-up and long-term planning of the CoP.

Table 11: Guidance on activities and elements to include in the first CoP meeting

Beginning of the meeting
<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. Greeting and introduction; 2. Explanation of the logistics and agenda (online or in-person); 3. Round of introductions with stakeholders and CoP Coordinator and Moderator;
Middle of the meeting
<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. Validate pre-identified objectives, mission and ambition (or LL's strategic agendas) of CoP with the stakeholders – refine together to ensure that these are aligned with the stakeholders' expectations; working towards a shared objective/vision is critical to community development. <p style="margin-left: 20px;">Questions to be answered by the stakeholders are:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • What topics and issues do we really care about? • What are the development challenges we want to address? • What outcomes do we want to focus on? • What is out of scope? • How is this domain connected to the organisation's strategy? • What is in it for us? • What kind of influence do we want to have? • How will we communicate the community's goals and achievements, and to whom? <p>The answers to these questions will help the community to develop a shared understanding of its objective, find its legitimacy in the organisation and engage the passion of its members (Brouwer et al., 2018)</p> <p> TIP! Consider use CoP point of departure moderation technique (Annex 2)</p>

2. Co-define the specific ways the community will operate, build relationships and grow. Establish the operating practice and knowledge system and take the example questions below as guiding (Brouwer et al., 2018):

Goals: Find the community's specific way to operate, build relationships, and grow.

- How will the community be organized and run?
- Is membership open, closed or something in between?
- What roles are members going to play?
- How will decisions be made?
- How often will the community meet?
- What kind of activities will generate energy and develop trust?
- What kind of behaviors can we expect from each other (respect, honest feedback, etc.)?
- How can the community balance the needs of various segments of members?

TIP! Consider use *Team purpose and culture moderation technique (Annex 2)*

3. Co-define the short and long-term value for the organisations and attending stakeholders, in connection with the identified needs and desired outcomes of the CoP. This can be done through a group reflection/discussion or through a survey during the meeting. The Value Matrix in Table 6 above can be used to identify shared values of the CoP (Koti et al., 2017)

Middle of the meeting (contd.)

4. Co-design the community in a way that it becomes an effective knowledge resource to its members.

Consider addressing the following questions in the first CoP meeting.

- How will community actions result in outcomes?
- What knowledge to share, develop, document?
- What kinds of learning activities to organize?
- How should we use collective learning, versus expert/apprentice, versus external research/expertise?
- What potential work groups could be created?
- Where are the sources of knowledge and benchmarks outside the community?
- How should we support members as both experts and learners?
- What are the benefits for members?

5. Map out the most important stakeholders and fill any gaps in terms of involvement of a particular organisation or person. Also discuss and consider the interest and power relations of stakeholders openly in a constructive and respectful manner, enabling everyone to share their perspective and willingness to contribute. Should any stakeholders not wish to take part as a result of disagreement or lack of interest, find a mutually beneficial way to uphold the relationship even with minor or no involvement in the CoP (i.e., through periodic email correspondence, one-on-one discussions with some of the partners, etc.).

End of the meeting

6. Summarise the discussions into a Community Charter, which will be agreed upon by all stakeholders involved in the CoP during this first meeting. Once it has been drafted and finalised, send around to all CoP Members, which will finalise the long-term design and accountability to the CoP (Koti et al., 2017).

7. Share any relevant documents or links to meeting evaluation – reserve time during the meeting for this and send after in a summary email.

8. Summarise the meeting and define the next steps together as a group.

2.5.1.2 In-Between CoP meetings

Table 12: Guidance on activities and elements to include in the in-between CoP meetings

Beginning of the meeting
<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. Greeting and introduction; 2. Checking-in or Warm-up activity with all stakeholders (See Annex 2: Moderation techniques).
Middle of the meeting
<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 3. Discussion on relevant topics as set-up in the project roadmap through moderation and engagement activities that enable co-creation, learning and knowledge exchange.
End of the meeting
<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 4. Summarise the meeting and define the next steps together as a group. 5. Share any relevant documents or links to a meeting evaluation – reserve time during the meeting for this and send after in a summary email. 6. Communicate any reminders.

2.5.1.3 Last CoP Meeting

Table 13: Guidance on activities and elements to include in the last CoP meeting

Beginning of the meeting
<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. Greeting and introduction; 2. Checking-in or Warm-up activity with all stakeholders (See Annex 2: Moderation techniques).
Middle of the meeting
<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 3. Discussion on: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Final resolutions/decisions; • Next steps for the community – future.
End of the meeting
<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 4. Summarise the meeting and define the next steps together as a group; 5. Share any relevant documents or links to a meeting evaluation – reserve time during the meeting for this and send after in a summary email; 6. Communicate any reminders and final decisions.

2.6 After each CoP meeting and yearly

2.6.1 Responsibilities of the Moderators / Coordinators

When the CoP meeting ends, the Moderator needs to make sure that the CoP brings added value to the project and its members. This means that the outcomes of the CoP meetings need to be collected, recorded and monitored and therefore the CoP participants need to fill in the evaluation form (see Annex 5: Evaluation form). In the case of a face-to-face CoP, it is advisable to ask participants to fill in the paper form during the meeting to ensure a high response rate. In the case of online CoP, the CoP Moderator will share a link to the online evaluation form directly at the end and after the meeting.

Coordinator & Moderator Checklist after CoP

- | Coordinator | Moderator |
|---|--|
| <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Fill in CoP report | <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Distribute evaluation form |
| <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Keep participants engaged in between meetings | |
| <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Send out summary e-mail | |

Tip !
Using the *Checking in* moderation techniques in between two meetings to keep the CoP members engaged throughout the entire project.

You can find the instruction to this method in **Annex 2**

The CoP Moderator is also responsible for filling in the meeting report (See Annex 6: Template for CoP meeting reporting), which provides an overview of the goals, agenda, participants and main outcomes. The evaluation form, CoP report, together with the minutes of the CoP are crucial input for the work of WP2-3 in the B-WaterSmart project.

2.6.1.1 How to maintain stakeholder interest in between meetings?

To create and maintain the community feeling between CoP meetings, which occur only periodically throughout the project duration, it is important to keep the members engaged and interacting between the different meetings (Brouwer et al., 2018). This can be done by setting up activities at the end of the CoP where the participants can act on the lessons they learned in the previous CoP. Another option would be to use the Checking in moderation technique (see Annex 2: Moderation techniques). By setting up an online channel for CoP members (e.g., in Microsoft teams, SharePoint or WhatsApp), the CoP Moderator can regularly check in with the members by inquiring about their project goals and also current successes, as focusing on successes is important to keep members enthusiastic and, most importantly, engaged. CoP are often long-term focused, meaning that the main success is expected at the end of the project. However, paying attention to and celebrating small victories and wins throughout the duration of the CoP allow participants to stay motivated, as these successes demonstrate the short-term benefits and added value of the CoP.

2.6.1.2 Information sharing: online platform

All documentation (static or "live") related to the CoP will be made available in a common online area. It is the responsibility of the CoP Coordinator to make the documents available and keep them up to date. The CoP Coordinator may send a notification to the Living Lab mentor and owner when a new document or a new version of a previous document is made available.

Providing CoP documents and updating them is an important form of knowledge sharing, especially on lessons learned and best practices to implement for organisers, as well as new ideas, innovations and updates based on the specific CoP Living Labs.

2.7 Successful Meetings: Checklist for CoP Coordinators and Moderators

Before the meeting

1. Define roles and responsibilities of the CoP Coordinator, Moderator and stakeholders early on before the meeting, i.e., who will manage the meeting logistics, who will facilitate the meeting, what roles do the stakeholders have, if any. Also define a *rapporteur* and take notes within the template provided in Annex 6: Template for CoP meeting reporting.
2. Before the meeting, send out an email with:
 - a. a survey to better understand your stakeholders and their expectations so you can match them and adjust the meeting as necessary;
 - b. an invitation letter to motivate stakeholders to participate with an agenda invitation for their email calendar;
 - c. the meeting agenda, and any other important documents to prepare for the meeting, as well as outlining the desired outcomes;
 - d. the consent forms to be fulfilled and signed.

During the meeting

3. During the meeting, ensure everyone feels welcomed, able to share, in a safe space to engage (consider languages, backgrounds, culture, personalities) – ensure balanced opportunities for all to engage in their own preferred way through the different meeting activities and moderation techniques (e.g., individual reflection vs. group discussions).
4. Plan activities (see Annex 2: Moderation techniques) that enable trust, maximize transparency, mutual understanding, and facilitating ongoing reflection by embracing an intentional learning approach, and creating an enabling environment for informal and open discourse and dialogue (Koti et al., 2017).
5. Think out of the box – engage people in new ways with activities and engagement tools – this will enable more interaction, participation, attention, and recall of the meeting and objectives to carry the CoP forward and its activities.
6. Design all your meetings and activities with the user in mind, i.e., following a user-centric design approach. This means knowing your stakeholders well and planning activities and discussions of relevance.

End of the Meeting

7. Set actions at the end of the meeting(s) and consider taking actions between meetings.

8. Right before the end of the meeting, whether in-person or online, move through the following elements¹:
 - a. reflect with the group for 5-10 minutes on how they perceived the meeting (positive, negative, neutral, etc.); the CoP Moderator and participants take part;
 - b. evaluation forms – reserve time at the end of the meeting to make sure that everyone fills the form online/in-person to get the highest response rates;
 - c. further information on the topic;
 - d. contact information as needed.

After the meeting

9. Fill out meeting minutes in the CoP Reporting template (see Annex 6: Template for CoP meeting reporting) so that it is still fresh in your mind
10. Send out a summary email with:
 - a. the evaluation form to participants in case they did not fill it in during the meeting;
 - b. meeting minutes (on shared drive or as an attachment);
 - c. next steps and action items;
 - d. other relevant information on the project, contact info, etc.

2.8 Evaluation of the CoP: rationale and approach

Evaluating the CoP is not only necessary to measure its success in terms of output, but also to measure its functioning over time in terms of process. In particular, it allows for continuous learning and improvement of the CoP throughout the project, with the overall goal of identifying best practices for the CoP at the end of the project. The evaluation approach used in the B-WaterSmart project is based on the framework of Fulgenzi et al, 2020. The method used measures the maturity of the CoP, structures and processes that support the success of the CoP. Fulgenzi et al. (2020) based their assessment of CoP on the three key elements of CoP: Community, Domain, and Practice, and combined them with the goal of CoP, i.e., social learning.

Social learning takes place through social interaction, within social networks, and B-WaterSmart leads to a change in an individual's perspective (Fulgenzi, 2019; Fulgenzi et al., 2020). Combining these elements of social learning with the key elements of CoPs, three dimensions of CoP Social Learning Outcomes (CoP-SLO) can be defined: 1) interaction and engagement of stakeholders, 2) changes in stakeholder issue frames, and 3) stakeholder's awareness of their own role and those of others. A well-functioning CoP is expected to score high on these three CoP-SLO dimensions. The CoP-SLO elements are abstract and therefore difficult to measure. However, Fulgenzi et al. (2020) have identified key success factors that, if sufficiently present, should foster the CoPs-SLO dimensions. Per CoP-SLO dimension, 6 key success factors are identified:

1. organisational aspects, tools, artifacts;

¹ Information regarding items 9a to 9d can be shared via the PowerPoint slides or via the chat during an online meeting.

2. adequate meeting atmosphere;
3. stakeholder inclusion and engagement;
4. convergence on a shared perspective;
5. identification of opportunities and challenges;
6. generation of useful knowledge.

These key success factors are in turn operationalised through indicators and translated into questions in the evaluation form (see Annex 5: Evaluation form). Evaluating the CoP based on the approach of Fulgenzi et al. (2020) enables the identification of which success factors are sufficiently present in the CoP and which aspects deserve more attention. This allows to implement changes to the CoP meetings to improve their effectiveness as well as to draw overall lessons to successful co-creation in CoP.

CoP have been evaluated through two different categories of methods, namely, qualitative, often referring to ethnographic studies and anecdotal stories, and quantitative methods, using analysis and statistical methods. However, both approaches had limitations and in order to circumvent these limitations, Fulgenzi et al. (2020) put forward an evaluation framework focusing on the analysis of social learning outcomes of CoP.

The figure below displays the schematic representation of the evaluation conceptual framework, i.e., the development of the three dimensions of a CoP (community, domain, and practice) and its interrelations with the achievement of social learning outcomes (relational outcome, shared understanding, substantive outcome).

Figure 4: CoP evaluation: conceptual framework (Source: Fulgenzi et al., 2020)

2.9 Cross-Fertilisation CoP

To enhance and re-enforce mutual learning between the CoP organisers and stakeholders, cross-fertilisation or cross-learning meetings should take place at least 2-3 times throughout the project duration (Brouwer et al., 2018). The cross-learning moments can happen between:

Coordinators and Moderators on **engagement and moderation** and overall progress of the CoP, sharing best practices and lessons learned for Coordinator and community management;

Stakeholders on the different **topics** of the CoP and enabling further ideation and co-creation to achieve the project objectives and sharing across locations, and innovation.

Holding these meetings will strengthen and improve the overall learning of best practises and lessons learned between the organisers, as well as new ideas and concepts on science and technologies for stakeholders. These meetings will add value to the overall CoP by bridging the gaps across topics, networking and innovation potential (Brouwer et al., 2018).

KWR will work with WP1 to coordinate the design and implementation of these cross-fertilisation meetings in B-WaterSmart.

As mentioned earlier, Annex 5: Evaluation form provides a template for CoP meeting minutes that should be used to provide information for the evaluation of CoPs, to share the results of the meeting with participants, and to keep track of what was discussed. These reports are also an essential contribution to cross-fertilisation and learning between the different CoPs and are used to report on the cross-fertilisation meetings.

In summary, cross-fertilisation between CoP can occur between Moderators and Coordinators, as well as between the stakeholders. This can happen by making CoP materials and documents available online in an openly accessible way, as well as through specific cross-fertilisation meetings where knowledge exchange and transfer can occur.

3 Ethical issues and procedures for the CoP

The steps, methodologies and engagement channels proposed in the MS3 report will be planned with full respect to current EU Regulations on ethical procedures and data protection, namely the General Data Protection Regulation (EU) 2016/679, as well as follow best practices in EU research.

In order to ensure that the process of stakeholder mapping and engagement in B-WaterSmart is undertaken with due consideration of all relevant ethics implications and procedures, this deliverable was subject to a review by the Project Ethics Advisor. Furthermore, the guidelines and recommendations presented here are articulated with the EC Guidance Note on ethics and data protection and the B-WaterSmart Data Management Plan (D8.3), which specifies the procedures to be followed in relation to ethical issues and data protection throughout the Project, as well as the Dissemination and Communication Plan (D7.5), respectively submitted in March and February 2021. Moreover, CoP activities will be conducted in observance of the principles of the European Code of Conduct for Research Integrity: reliability, honesty, respect, accountability (ALLEA, 2017).

3.1 Handling of personal data

For the purposes of CoP meetings and other related activities, only name, organisation and contacts (address, phone and cell numbers, emails, personal and institutional webpages) will be collected. These are meant to be used throughout the Project to send information, updates, and useful documentation to CoP participants. They may be added to the Project newsletter and contact list for communication and dissemination (WP7), pending specific authorisation for that purpose. Any specific use for the different activities of the Project will be specified, and permission for data collection will always be granted in written form, under the terms of the GDPR, respecting the principles of human dignity, individual autonomy, privacy and confidentiality of personal data (sensitive information).

For the purposes of the CoP design and operation, the B-WaterSmart team does not anticipate that any collection of special categories of personal data (formerly known as sensitive data) on vulnerable social groups will be required. This research does not involve the collection and/or processing of sensitive personal data such as health, sexual lifestyle, ethnicity, political opinion, religious or philosophical conviction (GDPR, article 9, 1) and does not involve further processing of previously collected personal data, except for one specific situation – union trade membership - which is detailed below.

The categories of data that we anticipate will be handled at CoP meetings are detailed in the B-WaterSmart DMP. Personal data are amongst those admissible according to EU legislation, specifically situations in which “the personal data was manifestly made public by the individual” and/or “the explicit consent of the individual was obtained (a law may rule out this option in certain cases)” (European Commission, 2021).

Information on trade union membership might, however, be conveyed during the meetings, in the cases where the CoP member is a representative of the Union, or of a sectoral organisation (such as Farmers Association). This information will not be collected purposefully but could be raised by the participants themselves during discussions. In addition, information on political opinions might be conveyed by the participants during the meetings in relation to the issues discussed, such as water scarcity and management, and competing demands over water resources. Political stands will also be

explicit in the cases where the CoP members are parliamentary representatives (e.g., special environment commissions).

However, this situation is covered by the exceptions allowed by the EC, namely that

- the personal data was manifestly made public by the individual or
- the explicit consent of the individual was obtained.

In any case, the handling of personal data will follow the procedures outlined by the Project Data Management Plan (DMP; D8.3). The DMP was drafted taking into account the GDPR for the collection, storage and re-use of personal data. In the cases where the Project team members might realise the need to handle any type of sensitive personal data (due to unforeseeable circumstances), the use of these data will only be allowed following explicit consent of the individuals concerned.

Data in B-WaterSmart will be managed according to the FAIR principles (findable, accessible, interoperable, and re-usable). Since they result from publicly funded research, data produced within B-WaterSmart are considered a public good, produced for the public interest, and will therefore be made openly available with as few restrictions as possible in a timely and responsible manner that does not harm intellectual property and confidentiality. As per the Project DMP, data produced by the Project will be anonymised and aggregated before being analysed, and specific informed consent will be requested to CoP participants before any data release. This also means that stakeholders themselves (including CoP participants) will be able to cross-check and validate whether research data are accurately and comprehensively reported and analysed, in order to exercise their rights as protected by the EU legislation and the EU Charter of Fundamental Rights.

3.2 Stakeholder mapping: diversity and inclusion

The Project team will endeavour to balance gender in selecting CoP participants and in defining their roles in the engagement process, whenever feasible (e.g., as far as allowed by the structure of institutions represented). In addition, stakeholder maps will aim representing the diversity within the LL communities at the local level and as far as relevant for the purposes of the Project, in relation to the implementation of water-smart solutions, fulfilling the Sustainable Development Goals and responding to the strategic objectives and vision of B-WaterSmart. Most relevant will be the adequate representation of nationalities, cultures, and age groups in what concerns representatives of the civil society at the city, municipal and regional level. The LL owners and mentors are ultimately the responsible institutions for mapping and engaging the stakeholders, but the WP1 and WP5 teams are providing guidelines and recommendations to ensure this process is as socially diverse as possible.

Previously to the definition of the CoP's architecture on the present document, an internal report was issued to the Project partners (Milestone 3, February 2021), with the objective to provide specific guidance on how to map the stakeholders, consider the diversity of social actors and institutions, as well as the specific socio-economic context of each Living Lab. In coordination with the KWR team and WP1 leaders, the WP5 team (Society, Governance, Policy) will be responsible for accompanying the design and implementation of the CoP (T5.1), as well as the CoP meetings (T5.2), and will therefore ensure an adequate consideration of diverse interests, needs and concerns, including those of the most vulnerable social groups (e.g. from marginalised neighbourhoods) that might deserve special consideration when designing and implementing B-WaterSmart solutions, as well as consider

gender issues, in accordance with the best practices at international level and guidance from the European Commission.

The stakeholder mapping template provided in Annex 4 already considers MS3 guidance, as above stated, in that they seek a broad inclusion of stakeholders who represent the diversity of social, economic, and environmental realities of each of the six LLs of the Project. The stakeholder mapping process followed a series of stages, since B-WaterSmart started in September 2020, whereby information was collected from the LL owners and mentors (water utilities, municipalities, research institutions) on societal and governance issues, as well as the current state of policies concerning water management. It also considered the ongoing work from WP1 and WP6 on the definition and vision for water-smartness, as well as the LL strategic agendas developed.

It is therefore against this background of rich and detailed information that the stakeholder mapping is construed, but the process does not stop here. In order to ensure inclusive participation of the stakeholders, participants at the first CoP meeting (fourth trimester of 2021) will also be invited to contribute other suggestions for institutions and individuals to involve in following meetings and other CoP activities, namely Focus Groups meetings, following a snowballing methodology.

3.3 CoP meetings and data collection

The CoP will be constituted by representatives of institutions, businesses, sectoral organisations, NGOs, and local associations who will be formally invited as members according to a protocol agreed from the first meeting (Annex 7: Suggestions for designing a Protocol for CoP operation).

At least one CoP meeting will take place during each year of the Project, starting in the fourth trimester of 2021 with an online introductory meeting due to the restrictions related to the COVID-19 pandemics. It is anticipated that following meetings can be held in person. These meetings will be organised at the LL level, in the local language, by the LL representatives and local partners, and in accordance with the guidance of MS3, D1.1, and the Data Management Plan (D8.3).

Before each CoP meeting, as well as focus groups and workshops organised as part of the stakeholder engagement process in B-WaterSmart, a complete information sheet and an informed consent form will be sent to all the participants along with the invitation for each CoP meeting (by email). It will be verified before each meeting that every invitee accepted the terms of the consent forms, and when this is not the case any issues arising will be handled beforehand. A second form will ensure appropriate permission for collecting any photos, video images, recordings, as well as detail the specific purposes for the personal data collected. Both these documents were included as annexes with MS3 in a preliminary form and are now included as annexes to this document in their final and revised form (see Annex 8: Consent forms).

The information collected during the CoP meetings pertains perceptions and opinions on issues related to water management and scarcity in the EU and the regions concerned in the B-WaterSmart Project, as well as considerations about the adequacy and effectiveness of the water-smart solutions proposed by the Project, which will be presented and discussed at these events. This information will be collected through written notes, audio and video recordings, as well as through the online platform in use by the Project. It will therefore be used for eventual re-design and adjustment of the B-WaterSmart solutions, as well as for the dissemination of the Project results, such as publications in peer-reviewed journals and communications at specialised conferences. The information will be subject to qualitative analysis

by the social researchers involved in B-WaterSmart, in accordance with the best practices and ethical guidelines established by the European Sociological Association (ESA) and its national counterparts, and in full compliance with the EU regulations and procedures.

The CoP meetings and related events will be recorded to support the Project team in writing detailed minutes (only to be shared between the CoP members) and for the purposes of analysing the topics discussed. Specific and written permission for the use of intrusive methods, such as video and audio recordings, will be sought from each CoP participant at every instance, and should any special circumstance arise where we need to use the image and audio files for purposes such as publicising the Project on the website. In any case, the original files will only be available to Project members.

3.4 Non-EU countries

B-WaterSmart involves an extra-EU partner (Norway: beneficiaries Bodø municipality, SINTEF, NTNU, Krüger-Kaldnes, Techni). As it is stated in the first version of the DMP submitted in March 2021 (D8.3), the European Commission allows transfer of personal data to and from Norway without any special safeguards, meaning that transfers to specific countries, including Norway, will be assimilated to intra-EU transmissions of data (European Commission, 2021). Even though, the B-WaterSmart DMP establishes that “no raw data will be exported from the country in which it is collected without suitable anonymisation and aggregation”.

4 B-WaterSmart Innovation Alliance

4.1 What is BWS innovation alliance and what are its main objectives?

B-WaterSmart Innovation Alliance (InAll) is a capacity building activity focused on strategic planning. Capacity building, defined as the process by which organizations obtain, improve, and retain skills, knowledge, tools, and other resources, is key to internalise new cross-cutting approaches within the organization. Hence, the scope and objective of InAll are different from the BWS short training courses.

InAll is tailored for the BWS LL problem-owners to internalise and learn by doing how to use the BWS objective-oriented assessment framework as a key instrument of strategic planning.

B-WaterSmart Innovation Alliance will foster the exchange across the LL and will focus on the collaborative application, testing, and co-development of the framework for assessing water-smartness as an essential tool for defining and implementing strategic methodologies to assure water-smart systemic innovation.

InAll and CoP have a different objective, use different techniques and methodologies, and have different roles. The InAll carries out an activity of capacity building of the LL problem owners and co-creation. InAll participants are BWS partners and CoP participants include stakeholders that are not BWS partners. In the strategic plan development and water smartness assessment framework, LL problem owners will need data or information from stakeholders within local CoP (MS5).

What is InAll?

- ☑ It is a capacity building initiative on how to use the BWS objective-oriented assessment framework as a key instrument of strategic planning.
- ☑ It is also a key co-production instrument of BWS since its participants will actively contribute to the BWS assessment framework.
- ☑ It is targeted to the BWS primary problem owners.
- ☑ It is a pioneer initiative in European research projects: BWS LL problem owners will be front-runners!

According to the GA, the intended outcomes of the InAll are, for each LL problem-owners:

1. a strategic plan for water smartness: revise/refine strategic objectives and targets, assessment and diagnosis regarding the objective's compliance, comparison with defined targets, identification of improvement opportunities, exploring, selection and prioritisation of alternatives, and monitoring implementation;

2. capacitated organisations for using the BWS framework to support strategic planning, monitoring and decision-making.

InAll will apply the framework in two stages, according to the GA:

1. to test the prototype V0 version of the water-smartness assessment framework and provide recommendations for its refinement and transformation into a software tool;
2. to apply, demonstrate and start to implement the dashboard in the LL as a management support tool the dashboard version (Task 3.9; M37-M45).

This chapter aims at establishing guidelines for setting up the InAll and defining its main objectives. It expands on the objectives as described in the GA, provides more information about the InAll approach, responsibilities, and potential benefits for the BWS LL owners, and sets up a preliminary implementation planning.

InAll will focus on the planning process, rather than on technology. It is tailored to **BWS LL problem-owners**:

Organisations to be capacitated within InAll:

BWS Living lab	BWS LL primary problem-owner
Alicante LL	AMAEM (Águas Municipalizadas de Alicante)
Bodø LL	BODØ (Bodø municipality)
East Frisia LL	OOWV
Flanders LL	DeW (De Watergroep)
Lisbon LL	CML (Lisbon Municipality)
Venice LL	VERI (Veritas)

More than a commitment, BWS InAll is a great opportunity for all the BWS problem-owners to internalize a systemic and systematic assessment-based practice to support water smartness strategic planning. Participating organisations will be able to better understand their current water smartness status, aspects to improve, and compare alternative paths / processes for improvement. More than alternative technologies, focus will be on soft approaches, dealing for instance (but not exclusively) with governance issues. Starting from the current status of each participant, from their current priority setting and on the on-going BWS WP2 and WP3 work, InAll participants will be able to further develop their strategic planning supported on the BWS assessment framework.

InAll main learning outcomes are:

What are the InAll learning outcomes?

- ☑ What to use the framework for?
- ☑ How to apply the framework in practice in order to get the best out of it?
- ☑ How to carry out a diagnosis, assessment, monitoring and comparison, in the context of strategic planning, in an assisted way, based on the BWS Assessment Framework?
- ☑ How to share experiences in a truly learning-by-applying way?
- ☑ How the LL owners can explore different strategic options, measures, paths?

BWS InAll:

- brings together “problem owners”/water utilities and R&I partners with a common interest focused on the creation of innovative knowledge;
- enables the implementation of the LL strategic agendas by a systematic water-smartness assessment;
- enables capacity building on water-smartness assessment through co-development and co-learning;
- demonstrates the effectiveness and added value of this type of instrument in the context of European Research and Innovation projects.

The basic rationale of InAll is to carry out the capacity building process on water-smart assessment and strategic planning through co-development and co-learning.

While in T1.3 the scope is to provide short courses for all BWS stakeholder, for a first insight about the multiple BWS products and other outcomes, the InAll is supported on the actual cases of each BWS LL problem-owners. Each team problem owner will work on its own case, with the support and guidance from LNEC (as T1.4 leader) and of the respective mentor.

4.2 What is the consortium’s past experience in similar innovation alliances?

Innovation alliances involve partners who use complementarities of resources, knowledge and experience for the creation of new technologies, products and services, and where engagement depends on the expectancies in jointly creating an added value, through co-creation processes and group dynamics (O’Donnell et al., 2018).

InAll builds on the consortium’s past experience, particularly LNEC’s. This type of instrument has been in use by LNEC since 2000. Figure 5 outlines past work and experience, for over 20 years, in peer- to-

peer innovation alliances with water utilities in several areas of application, such as infrastructure asset management (4 projects involving 64 utilities), water and energy (4 projects involving 58 utilities), reliability, safety and resilience (2 projects involving 22 utilities) and water quality, treatment and reuse (2 projects involving 26 utilities). This experience, combined with the expertise of the other partners, constitutes a fundamental background for the implementation of InAll.

Figure 5: R&D&I areas: Peer-to-peer Innovation Alliances with water utilities

4.3 Planning of InAll implementation

4.3.1 InAll roles

One of the essential steps in establishing innovation alliances is to make very clear from the onset, what are the roles of each partner involved. The implementation of InAll is coordinated by LNEC, involves the participation of LL problem-owners and their respective LL mentors.

Role of INALL leader - LNEC

- develop the phased program;
- coordinate activities;
- develop and make available documentation and tools to support the development of the work;
- provide support to LL mentors;
- analyse information;
- ensure security and confidentiality in information sharing.

Role of LL mentors

The LL mentors will be key to support the management of the LL participation in InAll, namely ensuring the development of the work within the LL in each phase, the communication with the developers of BWS, including the framework and dashboard, as well as the InAll leaders. Their role will be to:

- act as facilitators;
- analyse information;

- provide support and supervision;
- ensure security and confidentiality in information sharing.

Role of LL problem-owners

For each LL problem-owner, it should be a 2-4 people's team lead by a responsible person to be appointed by the LL BWS problem-owner.

The responsible person will lead the process within the LL and will ensure the transmission and dissemination of results within the LL. His/her role is to:

- conduct programmed activities ensuring that all members fully accomplish InAll tasks;
- ensure the involvement of elements belonging to different sectors of the organisation;
- report the progress of each phase;
- enable the coordination and dialogue with the other LL partners, LL COP and solution providers.

The participating team will be responsible for developing the LL work, including the application and testing of the BWS assessment framework and dashboard, development of the plan, and for liaison with the other sectors of the utility or other entities that may be involved in the work progress, the use of results and the production of necessary data or information.

It is strongly recommended that the InAll team includes participation of at least a strategic decision-maker or direct advisor and the team leader of BWS problem-owner. Stability of the team designated throughout the InAll is recommended.

In order to ensure that the work program established will be fulfilled, a preliminary stage is considered in M18, prior to InAll kick-off, in order to define the participating team, and responsible person for each LL problem-owner.

4.3.2 Common phased schedule

The InAll follows a common five-phased schedule, to facilitate strategic planning common guidance, application of the BWS assessment framework, clarifications and reporting by each LL team with responsibilities assigned. Besides, the tasks included in the program will provide opportunities for sharing experiences, debating sessions and provision of improvement recommendations. The work developed by each LL problem-owner will be tailored to its specific context and needs.

Each phase has a particular work program specifying the work to be developed by the LL team, including dedicated training related to the partial objectives to be reached in the phase.

Each phase of the work program includes a plenary session of start-up and programming, addressed to all LL participant teams, followed by a training action focused on the work that will be carried out in that phase, with technical support from the InAll or task leaders or representatives, related to the work planned for the phase. During each phase there will be one intensive hands-on joint workshop or session for the participating teams, to provide opportunity for sharing experiences and discussions. Each phase ends with a plenary meeting to present and discuss partial results, which coincides with the start-up meeting of the next phase. Decision on whether plenary meetings will be carried out in a

face-to-face or virtual format depends on the pandemics situation and will be made by consensus among participants.

As a preliminary proposal, the following phases are planned as follows:

Figure 6: Five-phased schedule for implementing BWS InAll

4.3.3 InAll work program

The work program for each phase is described as follows. The manpower effort indicated corresponds to a realistic estimate so that every participating organisation gets full long-term benefits from InAll, seen as an opportunity offered by the project to the LL owners. This estimate exceeds on average by about 1.6 PM the time allocated in the GA for each LL owner. Participants are free to dedicate only the contractual time effort defined in the GA for InAll activities. However, this would render a limited outcome only (with a focus more on short-term benefits for the participating team rather than on long-term ones for the organization as a whole).

PHASE 1 – Kick-off | 2 Months [M19-M20]

1 - Establishment of the strategic planning scope within InAll for each BWS LL problem-owner, including time horizon for planning and analysis and the geographical area of analysis.

2 - Analysis of the work already in place in the LL, survey of existing related processes and plans, strategic agenda or strategic plan (linked with Task 1.5 and D1.4).

3 - Detailed planning of activities.

Meetings and training: plenary meeting and training dedicated to BWS planning process

Effort: about 12 working days per team member is anticipated.

PHASE 2 – Strategic assessment | 3 Months [M21-M23]

1 - Analysis of the LL strategic agenda or plan in the face of water smartness.

2 - Identification of BWS strategic objectives and definition of the BWS assessment system for each LL:

- strategic objectives
- criteria; metrics; reference values
- identification of data needs

- first critical analysis of BWS assessment framework v0

3 - Strategic assessment

- data collection

- metrics assessment for the current situation

- problems identification from the assessment

4 - Analysis of the framework and feedback to WP6 - T6.3 (D1.3)

Meetings and training: plenary meeting and training dedicated to BWS assessment framework

Workshop for hand-on and sharing experiences

Effort: about 15 working days per team member is anticipated.

PHASE 3 – Diagnosis | 10 Months [M24-M33]

1 - Analysis of the internal and external context; definition of scenarios; SWOT analysis

2 - Future analysis based on the strategic assessment carried out and on the SWOT analysis

3 - Problems' identification

4 - Recalculation of the metrics using the early version of the dashboard from WP3 - T3.9, considering D3.3.

Meetings and training: plenary meeting and training dedicated to the diagnosis and BWS dashboard

Workshop for hand-on and sharing experiences

Effort: about 15 working days per team member is anticipated.

PHASE 4 – Strategic plan | 12 Months [M34-M45]

1 - Analysis of final version of the BWS assessment

2 - Identification and analysis of alternative strategies, including developments in BWS

3 – Assessment and comparison of the formulated alternatives with the dashboard (T3.9, D3.6)

4 - Definition of strategies

5 - Analysis to identify necessary changes in the strategic plan, when applicable

6 - Identification of necessary resources to implement the strategies

7 - Definition of procedures for monitoring and review of the plan

8 - Production of (revised) strategic plan

Meetings and training: plenary meeting and training dedicated to the approach for comparison and development of alternatives

Workshop for hand-on and sharing experiences

Effort: about 15 working days per team member is anticipated.

PHASE 5 – Production of InAll recommendations | 3 Months [M46-M48]

1 - Development of procedures to facilitate the dashboard use in the LL problem-owners as a management support tool.

2 – Identification of lessons learnt in InAll and recommendations for other users (D1.5).

Meetings: plenary meeting

Effort: about 6 working days per team member is anticipated.

5 References

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Annex 1: Engagement tools for on-line meetings

The tools for engagement below can be used for a variety of on-line engagement and moderation opportunities. We have highlighted a selection of the most effective and tested tools based on the intended use for CoP. We recommend the following in choosing the best online tool for your CoP:

- 1) Use the tool that you are most comfortable or familiar or who already have a licence. For example, if you or your company have experience with using Microsoft Teams internally and externally to your company, then we recommend going with that tool as it will reduce the planning and effort needed to coordinate a meeting.
- 2) If you are not already familiar with any of the tools below, the following shortlist is recommended based on the online tool's ease of use and use experience (noted with a star in the table below):
 - a. [Webinar Meeting Platform: Zoom Meetings](#) - Zoom is easy to use and tried and tested by a wide online community. Zoom is superior to competitors with its built-in polling functionality, connection stability, breakout-rooms and ease of logging into a meeting for external partners. Their security issues have been largely resolved; however, some companies have still banned its use. There are costs associated with its use, so please look into these as well as the free limited version.
 - b. [Collaboration Tools: GroupMap](#) – GroupMap is a great tool for mapping, vision setting and online collaboration on priorities, SWOT analyses and more. It is user-friendly and enables engagement during online meetings, with multiple templates already created for all types of meeting objectives. Furthermore, you can easily access the PDFs of the worksheets after the meeting. There are costs associated with its use, so please look into these as well as the free limited version.
 - c. [Polling or Surveying: Mentimeter or Slido](#) – If the online meeting tool you are using does not have a built-in polling system, then Mentimeter or Slido are great alternatives. Both platforms enable visually pleasing and simple online engagement through polling, quizzes with visual data analytics through graphs, barcharts and wordclouds. This can help to make a decision, highlight current knowledge levels, and enable your participants to give their opinions to shape your meeting. There are costs associated with its use, so please look into these as well as the free limited version.

***Please Note:** All tools below have outline data and privacy issues on their websites. If your company or institution is concerned with privacy, data and security in using these tools, we advise to verify your specific needs by visiting the website of any of the tools recommended below.

Legend:

Recommended	Used by KWR	Not yet explored /used to a full extent
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Tool	Pros & Cons	Features	Reference Photo
Webinar/Meeting Platforms			
<p><u>Zoom</u></p> <p><u>Photo Source</u></p>			

<p><u>GoToMeetings</u></p>	<p>Pros:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Can offer recordings afterwards with a link • On-Demand meetings with a simple URL • Integrated into email platforms • Up to 250 participants <p>Cons:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Control panel/portal not user-friendly • No raise hand function • No breakout rooms • Unstable connection compared to other tools • Limit to camera/video visibility <p>More information</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Application Sharing • Audio conferencing via phone and computer • Drawing tools • Full desktop sharing • Instant Messaging • Instant meetings with a single click • Integrated scheduling with Microsoft Outlook® • Join from Mac, PC, iPad®, iPhone® or Android • One-click high-definition HDFaces™ video • One-time scheduled meetings • Recording • Recurring meetings <p>Source</p>	<p>Photo Source</p>
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<p><u>Webex</u></p>	<p>Pros:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Meeting encryption • Basic features: up to 500 participants • Raise hand function • Collaboration and annotation tools • Breakout/interactive sessions • Easy to use <p>Cons:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Webex requires a lengthier registration and check in • No meeting registration reports • The menu system is not intuitive • Some issues with non-Webex users to connect via audio • Complicated to navigate compare to competition • Extra fee for “call-me” feature • Interface could be modernized • Expensive compared to competitors <p>More information here and More Information</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • “Call me” Feature • Recording • Polling • Whiteboard • Transcription (only in English) <p>Source</p>	<p>Photo Source</p>
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<p><u>Microsoft Teams</u> (for meetings and webinars)</p>	<p>Pros:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Useful chat options (can send documents) • In sync with Microsoft Office suite • Raise hand function • Great for internal communication and meetings <p>Cons:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Not as good as competitors for external meetings • No built-in possibility during a meeting to go into breakout rooms (can do it through a Team/Channel, but complicated set-up) • Not-so-simple login to a Teams meeting (additional steps) • No built in polling for meetings, so need to use external app or program 	<p>Latest features 2020</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Enable spell check • Channel notification is simple using ... button • Consult > transfer the call • Focus option on slides shares • Meeting notes • Meet now and schedule into channel top right corner • Channel setting, updates, and notification at the top right corner <p>Some updates are coming soon:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Speaker attribution for live captions • Live transcript for the meeting which can be used for review after the meeting • Increase from 300 to 1000 participants in interactive meetings • Whiteboard - faster load, sticky notes, and drag and drop capabilities • Reflect - new polling apps in MS Teams channels • Virtual breakout rooms <p><u>Source</u></p>	<p><u>Photo Source</u></p>
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Collaboration Tools / Project Ideation and Management

Decidim + BigBlueButton

- Pros:
- Integrates in a coherent environment tools for supporting participative processes (e.g., collection of ideas, needs, debates and discussions) and on-line meetings, enabling both real-time and anytime online collaboration.
 - Highly customizable collaboration space
 - Based on open-source software
 - Meeting encryption
 - User and content moderation
 - Video conferencing up to 150 simultaneous participants
- Cons:
- Some connection issues with some versions of Safari web browser

- Participative processes
- Blog
- Meetings
- Surveys
- Video Conferencing
- Chat
- Emojis
- Electronic Hand Raising
- Polls/Voting
- Presentation Streaming
- Presentation Tools
- Record session
- Screen Sharing
- Breakout Rooms
- Collaborative whiteboard
- Pdf export of the whiteboard

The image shows two screenshots of the Decidim platform. The top screenshot displays a dashboard titled 'QUALI ATTIVITA' E SERVIZI?' with a map of Italy and several activity cards for different projects. The bottom screenshot shows a workshop page titled 'C'è speranza oltre gli ulivi' with a detailed agenda for an event.

<p><u>Mural</u></p>	<p>Pros:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Great for real time and any time online collaboration and co-creation • Visually attractive for brainstorming • Hosts a variety of templates for collaboration and engagement for projects / project management • Integration into existing workflows <p>Cons:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Need to attend a training prior to use (for effective use, it is best to attend one of the free webinars and to test it out) • Needs a trial run for participants to get used to the interface 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Free trial (30 days) • Sticky notes and text • Shapes and connectors • Icons • Frameworks • Images and gifs • Drawing • Meeting timer • Summon group members to location on mural • Outline your meeting with templates • Lock items on the mural board • Private mode • Sharing, commenting, chat, quick talk <p><u>Source</u></p>	<p>The screenshot shows the Mural web application interface. At the top, it says 'Team Brainstorming'. The main workspace contains a circular diagram with several sticky notes attached to it. The notes include 'creative process', 'collaborative culture', 'remote collaboration', 'facilitation management', 'real-time collaboration', and 'digital transformation'. Participant avatars for 'Halley', 'David', 'CJ', and 'Seema' are visible around the diagram. A toolbar at the bottom left includes icons for drawing, erasing, and text. A 'remote collaboration' sticky note is also present.</p> <p><u>Photo Source</u></p>
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<p><u>GroupMap</u></p> <p>Photo source</p>			
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<p><u>Remo</u></p>	<p>Pros:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Great tool for collaboration and interaction for online meetings • Exciting/visual and looks great for fostering more dynamism in online/virtual meetings • Enables connections between attendees • Ability to have numerous different conversations throughout a room <p>Cons:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Expensive • Registration page not intuitive <p>More information</p> <p>More information</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Host Controls • Alerts/Notifications • Auto Framing • Automatic Transcription • Branding • Chat Export • Communication Tools • Customizable Branding • Electronic Hand Raising • File Sharing • HD Audio • Host Controls • Polls/Voting • Presentation Streaming • Presentation Tools • Private Chat • Q&A Sessions • Real-Time Chat • Record & Playback Ability • Reporting/Analytics • Screen Sharing • Two-Way Audio & Video • User Profiles • Video Conferencing • Webcasting <p>Source</p> <p>Updated features 2020</p>	<p>Photo source</p>
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<p>Trello</p>	<p>Pros:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Good for coordinating projects, topics, content planning • Easy to add content and tag colleagues • Can consolidate information on a specific task and project • Project checklist • Easy upload feature • Keep track of to-do lists • Share files with your team members • Ability to collaborate • Flexible <p>Cons:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Need to define an approach that works for your team, or could get messy • Lacking integration with other software • Difficult for big projects <p>More information</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Task scheduler and prioritisation • Shared team calendar • Time tracking • Attachment options • Communication • File sharing • Team dashboards <p>Source</p>	<p>Photo Source</p>
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<p><u>Padlet</u></p>	<p>Pros:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Good for mind-mapping and brainstorming ideas • Easy to set up and use • Design thinking • Users can collaborate and share media easily • Good for virtual group-work • Online “bulletin board” <p>Cons:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • None of relevance <p><u>More information</u></p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Available in 29 languages, with more being added • Collaborate with users from around the globe • Working towards greater accessibility every day • Add posts with one click, copy-paste, or drag and drop • Works the way your mind works - with sight, sound, and touch • Changes are autosaved • Simple link sharing allows for quick collaboration • Invite others to contribute - signup not required • Work with unlimited contributors • Give read-only, writing, moderator, or admin access, revoke at any time • Watch updates appear instantly across devices • Privacy and security options • Compatible with most file types and devices • Good customer support <p><u>Source and more information</u></p>	<p><u>Photo Source</u></p>
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<p>Zoom Breakout Rooms</p>	<p>Pros:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> Built into Zoom Great for breaking out into smaller groups for discussions <p>Cons:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> If recording, need to click record again when into breakout rooms Needs moderate training to apply effectively and in a timely manner Limited number of participants in each Breakout Room 	<p>See Zoom features above</p>	<p>The screenshot shows the Zoom Breakout Rooms settings menu. It lists four breakout rooms (Breakout Room 1 to 4) with an 'Assign' button next to each. Below this is a 'Breakout Rooms - Not Started' dialog box with several options: 'Move all participants into breakout rooms automatically' (checked), 'Allow participants to return to the main session at any time' (checked), 'Breakout rooms close automatically after: 5 minutes' (with a dropdown), 'Notify me when the time is up' (checked), and 'Countdown after closing breakout room' (checked). At the bottom of the dialog, there is a 'Set countdown timer: 60 seconds' and buttons for 'Recreate', 'Options', 'Add a Room', and 'Open All Rooms'. The 'Options' button is highlighted with a red box. The background of the screenshot shows a Zoom meeting interface with the word 'Alert' visible.</p> <p>Photo source</p>
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<p>SharePoint</p>	<p>Pros:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Good for file storing and sharing for collaborative projects • Connected to Microsoft Office • Permission management • Contact groups • Version history • Can lock documents upon final revision <p>Cons:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Need to be invited • Not so user-friendly • If files are used and edited from here, need to upload new files, so could create confusion • Advanced configurations – administration not straightforward • Unappealing aesthetically <p>More information</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • File sharing • Synchronise with OneDrive • Integration with PowerApps and BI • File storage and organisation • Multiple devices and/or browsers <p>More information</p>	<p>Photo Source</p>
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<p>Microsoft Teams (for collaboration)</p>	<p>Pros:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Great for storing and collaborating on documents • Easy to edit and collaborate on Word Documents • Can share a collaborative document in a Teams meeting and having people work on / add information • Can make different channels for different projects • Include other apps all in one spot (e.g., Trello) <p>Cons:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Not so easy to track changes and see what has been done • Not great for working on multiple documents at once • Some formatting is lost when uploaded to Teams 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Communication driven by instant messaging and audio/video chat • Live meetings and on-demand recordings • Integrations with Office 365 apps such as Planner as well as third-party services • Mobile app for on-the-go teamwork – access across all devices <p><u>Source</u></p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • File sharing and viewing for editing • Collaborate live in real time • Tagging colleagues in chat and in Teams channels (reduces emails) • Collaborate internally and externally <p><u>Source</u></p>	<p><u>Photo Source</u></p>
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Polling/Survey Tools		
<p><u>Polling built into Zoom</u></p>	<p>Pros:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Easy to use • Built in • Simple interface <p>Cons:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Is not visible in recording of meeting or webinar, only to the live viewers 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Single choice or multiple-choice polling • Launch one poll at a time or multiple • Sharing results with the audience <p><u>Source</u></p>
<p><u>Mentimeter</u></p>	<p>Pros:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Good for polling word clouds, bar graphs • Easy to set up • Data visualisation • Live results • Easy to connect and vote <p>Cons:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Limited to 3 questions for free version 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Interactive presentations • 13 interactive question types including word clouds and quiz • Your audience uses their smartphones or a separate tab on their web browser to connect to the presentation where they can answer questions • Visualize responses in real-time • Share and export your results • Translate • Compare data over time with trends • Profanity filters <p><u>Source</u></p>
<p><u>Photo Source</u></p>		
<p><u>Photo source</u></p>		

<p>Slido <p>Photo source</p>			
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<p>Kahoot</p>	<p>Pros:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Good for polling, quizzes, live results • Gamified interface • Colorful, vibrant • Easy interface • Adaptable for various age levels • Good for educational purposes • Multiple users in mobile app <p>Cons:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Tailored for younger crowd of students • Some additional barriers to connect and poll (need to put name, enter a code, then poll) • Interface is cluttered and overwhelming • Nicknames so difficult to track • Not able to integrate into presentations ahead of time <p>More information</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Minutes to create a game from scratch • Question bank • Templates • Live via video • Paced challenges • Timer • Assign and review • Create and share outside of live interface, i.e. before or after a meeting <p>Source</p>	<p>Photo source</p>
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<p>Google Forms</p>	<p>Pros:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Easy and user-friendly set up • Can generate excel sheet of responses • Data visualisation • Free • Can customise response routes (i.e., if yes, go to Question 2) • Versions automatically saved to Google Drive <p>Cons:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • None of relevance • Limited templates <p>More information</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Free • Manage event registrations, quick polling, collect information • Use your own photo or logo • Create or respond on the go • Organised data analytics and visualisation • Add collaborators <p>Source</p>	<p>Photo source</p>
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<p>Doodle Poll</p>	<p>Pros:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Recognised method of finding a date for large groups • Easy to use and send out • Free • Convenient • Calendar integration • Avoid scheduling mistakes • Skip many emails to schedule <p>Cons:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • None of relevance • If you have many dates, scrolling feature gets too long and hard to view <p>More information</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Visibility • Time zones • Scheduling collaborative • Simplify updates • Manage reminders • Doodle Pro • Integrations with Zoom <p>Source</p>	<table border="1"> <thead> <tr> <th></th> <th>Fri 9</th> <th>Mon 12</th> <th>Tue 13</th> </tr> </thead> <tbody> <tr> <td>3 participants</td> <td>2:30 PM</td> <td>over lunch</td> <td>10:45 AM</td> </tr> <tr> <td>David</td> <td>✓</td> <td>✓</td> <td>✓</td> </tr> <tr> <td>Alice</td> <td>✓</td> <td>✓</td> <td>✓</td> </tr> <tr> <td>Richard</td> <td>✓</td> <td>✓</td> <td>✓</td> </tr> <tr> <td>Your name</td> <td><input type="checkbox"/></td> <td><input type="checkbox"/></td> <td><input type="checkbox"/></td> </tr> <tr> <td></td> <td>1</td> <td>3</td> <td>0</td> </tr> </tbody> </table> <p>Photo Source</p>		Fri 9	Mon 12	Tue 13	3 participants	2:30 PM	over lunch	10:45 AM	David	✓	✓	✓	Alice	✓	✓	✓	Richard	✓	✓	✓	Your name	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>		1	3	0
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3 participants	2:30 PM	over lunch	10:45 AM																												
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<p>Survey Monkey</p>	<p>Pros:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Templates built-it • Affordable • Tools to configure and customise • Several languages available • Simple links for use <p>Cons:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Costs money • Limited integration of apps <p>More information</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Multiple question types • Trend tracking • Automatic reminders • Customizable • Document storage • Integrations with email and social media and more • Email response tracking • Permission management • Real-time feedback • Recurring surveys • Data export • Daily email updates • Customizable survey links • Password-protected surveys • Collaborative survey editing <p>More information</p>	<p>Photo source</p>
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Annex 2: Moderation techniques

Annex 2 aims to support CoP Coordinators with explanations of various moderation techniques for CoP meetings over the course of the project. Each meeting will require a different set of activities to engage the stakeholders and will require different activities as the project progresses. As such, the moderation techniques are categorised per meeting element and/or activity in sequential order (i.e., introduction, setting the scene, defining scope and direction, brainstorming, making knowledge explicit, and decision making) to make it easier for the CoP Coordinator to select a suitable moderation technique. Further explanation will be given for each moderation technique with online or in-person specifics. This overview draws upon KWR's work in the STOP-IT (Brouwer et al., 2018; Freitas et al., 2018), BINGO (Brouwer et al., 2018), NextGen (Andrews et al., 2021), and WaterMining (Dirkse-Hulscher & Talen, 2007; Dosière & Wilems, 2016; UNICEF, 2015) projects, and a literature scan (Koti et al., 2017). On the next page a decision tree can be found for selecting the right type of moderation technique for conducting CoP meetings.

Moderation Techniques for:

1. [Introduction](#)
2. [Energise](#)
3. [Setting the scene](#)
4. [Defining the scope and direction](#)
5. [Brainstorming](#)
6. [Making knowledge explicit](#)
7. [Decision-making](#)

Figure 7 Decision tree for moderation techniques

Moderation techniques for introduction

Introduction techniques and “ice-breakers” are most suitable for the first round of CoP meetings or meetings which have many new participants.

Successful CoP require an open environment where the participants feel safe and can build trust among each other. Therefore, it is important that the participants get to know each other in formal and informal methods.

The following moderation techniques can facilitate such introductions:

Overview

- a. [Welcome coffee and coffee corners](#)
- b. [Interviewing](#)
- c. [The elevator pitch](#)
- d. [Single word introductions](#)
- e. [Picture introductions](#)
- f. [Checking-in](#)
- g. [Campfire](#)

MODERATION TECHNIQUE

Welcome Coffee and Coffee corners

WHAT

Welcome Coffee and coffee corners aim to stimulate interactions between the participants and help breaking the ice (Freitas et al., 2018).

HOW

A welcome coffee should be hosted at the beginning of the meeting by setting up coffee corners. This gives participants the opportunity to network and get to know each other upon arrival. The coffee corners should remain available during the session to create a more informal setting and to stimulate continuous interaction and networking in a natural manner during the working session. Participants can take a break when needed and discussions can continue over the coffee breaks.

BENEFITS

- Saves time through avoiding formal introductions
- Facilitates networking and introduction in an informal manner
- Helps to maintain the energy

ONLINE TIP

This technique can also be used in online sessions through having separate breakout sessions at the beginning of the meeting. This does require more planning from the CoP facilitator to assign the incoming participants to different breakout rooms. There should also be a moderator in each session to facilitate the conversation. The coffee corners during the online session can be substituted by having coffee breaks in separate breakout sessions during the meeting.

MATERIALS NEEDED

- Drinks: Coffee, Tea, Water
 - Snacks: cookies, fruit or other easy to eat snacks
 - Cups and napkins
-

TIPS

MODERATION TECHNIQUE

Interviewing

MODERATION TECHNIQUE

The elevator pitch

MODERATION TECHNIQUE

Single word introductions

WHAT

The single word introduction is an ice-breaker technique which can be done in small groups or with all the CoP participants (Freitas et al., 2018).

HOW

The participants choose from a pile of cards a card with a single word on it and are asked to tell a story about themselves involving the selected word.

BENEFITS

- Fun and creative ice-breaker
- Keeps introductions brief
- Stimulates participation and discussion

MATERIALS NEEDED

- Paper cards with one word
 - Or words displayed on a screen to all participants and they are asked to choose one
-

ONLINE TIP

This introduction technique can also be used in online CoPs. This requires the CoP moderator to display multiple words via a shared screen and to ask or assign a word to all the participants.

TIPS

MODERATION TECHNIQUE

Picture introductions

WHAT

Choosing a picture to introduce yourself and/or to illustrate your current mood as an ice-breaker introduction activity.

HOW

The CoP moderator prepares a set of thematically and locally relevant pictures. There should be more pictures than participants, so each participant has the option to select a picture that speaks most to them. When all the participants are present, the CoP moderator asks the participants to introduce themselves and the reason for choosing the specific picture (Freitas et al., 2018).

BENEFITS

- Allows everyone to introduce themselves
- Engaging and creative

CONS

- Time consuming in larger groups

ONLINE TIP

This activity can also be recreated online. The CoP moderator can display a number of images on screen and ask the participants to pick one and to introduce themselves by unmuting and turning on their camera.

TIPS

MATERIALS NEEDED

-
- Thematically relevant pictures on paper or displayed via a shared screen

MODERATION TECHNIQUE

Checking-in

WHAT

This technique is about checking-in with participants at the beginning of a meeting using a specific pre-determined question.

BENEFITS

- Helps facilitating a sense of community in between the meetings
- Fun and engaging way to break up the working day
- Facilitates communication between the members of a CoP

ONLINE TIP

This method has been designed for ease of use during online meetings. Simply display the questions via a shared screen and ask participants to unmute and turn on their camera when it is their turn to speak. The moderator can facilitate and ensure everyone has answered.

In case this method is used in between meetings, people can answer by writing in the channel chat.

HOW

The goal is to check-in with participants at the beginning of a meeting, and to do so at each subsequent meeting through the duration of the project. By checking-in, the CoP moderator poses questions that keep people engaged and develop a sense of openness among the participants. Examples of checking-in questions are:

- What are you planning to do today
- How are you feeling today?
- Would you like to share something that made you happy in the last week?

The moderator can start by answering the question and giving an example to make people feel comfortable.

MATERIALS NEEDED

- To prepare the questions and display them on a flipchart or on screen
 - Create a channel on an online meeting platform
-

MODERATION TECHNIQUE

Campfire

WHAT

In this method, participants choose words and then tell a story by building off of each others ideas at random, enabling a team building experience.

BENEFITS

- Facilitates social engagement and team building
- Can be used as informal training game
- Fun and creative
- Helps to make the diversity in peoples experience visible

CONS

- Takes a bit of time to warm up the participants to this storytelling approach – the moderator must ensure everyone feels comfortable and willing to share a fun story

ONLINE TIP

This method has been designed for ease of use during online meetings. Simply display the words via a shared screen and ask participants to unmute and turn on their camera when it is their turn to speak. The moderator can facilitate and ensure everyone has answered.

TIPS

HOW

The CoP moderator instructs all the participants before/during the meeting to think of words or phrases that can start the storytelling session. The words can be related to the project, or unrelated – they can be fun and engaging to have an exciting story. Then the moderator collects these words and displays them to the participants in a random order.

The CoP moderator then allows participants to view the words selected for a few seconds so that the participants have the time to associate potential stories with the words. The CoP moderator can then start the storytelling by choosing 1 word from the words displayed. The participants are asked to listen carefully and to think of ideas of how to follow on the storyline with another new word.

The CoP moderator then asks for a volunteer to go next. The next person chooses their own new word and to adds on to the story. This process continues until a full story thread exists and all the words have been exhausted. The moderator encourages the participants to be creative, and to take their time in telling a story. The moderator also tracks which words are being used and in which order to demonstrate the storyline that emerges.

MATERIALS NEEDED

- Paper and post-its
- Pens
- PowerPoint (if online)
- Online meeting program

Moderation techniques to energise

These techniques help to restore the energy during long meetings and to keep everybody engaged and active.

Overview

- a. [Picture sharing](#)
- b. [Meme theme](#)

MODERATION TECHNIQUE

Picture sharing

WHAT

A brief break in the meeting to re-energise again and feel closer to your colleagues.

HOW

All participants are asked to share a picture of their window view.

BENEFITS

- Provides a short break which restores participants' attention capacity.

MATERIALS NEEDED

- Camera/ phone with camera
 - Online meeting platform
-

ONLINE TIP

This method is meant for online meetings.

TIPS

MODERATION TECHNIQUE

Meme theme

WHAT

A brief break in the meeting to re-energise again and have fun with your colleagues.

HOW

The CoP moderator nominates one person who picks a theme (cute animals, grumpy cats, water, excitement, or another favourite meme). All the other team members are instructed to share a picture or meme related to the theme on the meeting platform.

BENEFITS

- Provides short break which restores the attention capacity of the participants.
- Makes for a fun meeting by sharing funny pictures and reducing any tension

MATERIALS NEEDED

- Online meeting platform
 - Internet
-

ONLINE TIP

This method is meant for online meetings.

TIPS

Moderation techniques for setting the scene

These methods are good to use at the beginning of a CoP (i.e. the first CoP meeting). Some of the techniques as seen in the overview below are suitable for the first CoP meetings, others can be used throughout the project at the start of any CoP meeting. These techniques help creating common ground and understanding between the participants.

Overview

- a. [Team purpose and culture](#)
- b. [CoP point of departure](#)
- c. [Project news so far/ News](#)
- d. [Asking the right questions](#)
- e. [LEGO PIECES with PESTLE bias](#)
- f. [Mapping spots](#)
- g. [SWOT world café](#)
- h. [Influence and motivation matrix](#)
- i. [“Futuribles” storytelling role play](#)

MODERATION TECHNIQUE

Team purpose and culture

WHAT

This exercise helps CoPs to jointly define why (purpose) and how (culture) they will work together

BENEFITS

- Lays the foundation for good collaboration
- Creates common ground and shared expectations
- Defines the purpose of the CoP

TIPS

ONLINE TIP

This method can be easily used online with an online meeting platform like Zoom or GoToMeetings. The moderator can use an online program like Mural or GroupMap for 2nd and 3rd steps

MATERIALS NEEDED

- Online meeting platform
- Poster
- Post-its
- Pen

HOW

The 1st step is for the CoP moderator to pose the following questions to the group and ask them to reflect on it:

- What is our task as a group?
- What is the goal of our CoP?
- How do we know that we have been successful? What added value are we bringing to the project and to the world?

This reflection can be done in a group discussion.

In the 2nd step, the CoP moderator asks the participants to individually reflect and write down their idea of the CoPs purpose in one sentence. Then, once individual reflection is done, the group can come together and by using the 20x20 rule, the participants will collectively create a CoP purpose of max 20 words in a discussion of 20 minutes. The CoP moderator warns the participants when they have 10, 5 and 2 minutes left. It is important to take time to acknowledge and celebrate the created CoP purpose.

The 3rd step is to jointly define the CoP culture. The CoP moderator will present an example of a good company culture. After presenting, the CoP moderator will ask the participants to write down as many words which they associate with a good working culture. Then the CoP moderator will instruct the participants to remove half of the words, leaving only the most important ones. Then the participants are asked to remove every word until each participant only has the three most important group culture elements (words) left. The participants are then invited to post/share these three words on the group map so they are visible for all participants. As a group, the participants will cluster all words based on any overlaps and meaning. The CoP moderator will ask the participants if there are elements missing once the clustering is done. If so, they can be added. Now the culture elements are complete. The participants have to jointly define what type of behaviour fits with these cultural elements. This has to be done for each identified element. Now the CoP purpose and culture are complete.

MODERATION TECHNIQUE

CoP point of departure

WHAT

This method helps the participants to define the aim, direction and first steps of the CoP.

BENEFITS

- Saves time through avoiding formal introductions
- Facilitates networking and introduction in an informal manner
- Helps to maintain the energy

ONLINE TIP

This method can be easily used online with discussion and an online meeting platform, as well as an online program or application like GroupMap, Mural or Google slides that everyone can access and edit.

TIPS

MATERIALS NEEDED

- Pen
 - Paper
 - Poster
 - Online meeting platform
-

HOW

The CoP moderator starts by explaining the purpose of this exercise: to create a joint vision on the direction and next steps taken by the CoP through answering 9 questions as a group, seen below. The next step is to create a place where discussion points that are not immediately relevant for the discussion are parked for later, to prioritise and focus this specific meeting. As a group, decide on how long you want to make this exercise and how much time you want to have for answering each question. The CoP moderator will be responsible for keeping the discussion focussed, time management and taking notes. Then it is time to answer the following questions:

- What is the overall purpose of the CoP?
- What is the desired outcome of the CoP?
- Who are we doing the CoP for?
- Who is involved in the CoP and what are their roles?
- What needs to happen by when?
- How will the team work together? Communicate and approach decision making?
- What does success look like? What does failure look like?
- How is the CoP connected to the rest of the project?
- How is the CoP connected to the other CoPs?

Answer these questions in bullet points

MODERATION TECHNIQUE

Project news so far

WHAT

A brief update to keep all the CoP participants informed about the progress of the rest of the project (Freitas et al., 2018).

BENEFITS

- Keep the CoP and participants connected and aware
- Allows for continuous synthesis
- Stimulates researchers to reflect on the progress and developments in the project
- Supports knowledge sharing across the project

ONLINE TIP

This method can be easily used online with discussion and an online meeting platform.

HOW

At the beginning of a CoP, the researchers of the project share the most important developments of the project. This could be done per work package. The updates should be short and not methodological or technical in depth, but provide a general overview. The updates could be presented in a “news updates” style in PowerPoint or solely an oral presentation. The CoP moderator should ask each participant to have maximum 10 words per slide for a maximum of 3-5 slides and 1 slide per minute of talking (i.e. 5 slides = 5 minutes presentation) and to use more pictures or illustrations. After the brief update there is time for a short discussion on the developments. It should be noted that this method is just to keep the participants updated on the progress of the projects and should not take too much time of the meeting.

MATERIALS NEEDED

- PowerPoint
 - Information on the project
-

MODERATION TECHNIQUE

Asking the right questions

WHAT

Asking the right questions is a way to identify the key issues that need to be addressed in the project (Dosière & Wilems, 2016).

BENEFITS

- Interactive way to identify potential obstacles in the project
- Facilitates learning and knowledge exchange
- Team building, respect and trust

ONLINE TIP

Can be easily done online through an online meeting platform, as well as by sharing the questions via shared screen through PowerPoint, Google Slides or a simple word document. The CoP moderator can also consider using a tool such as Mural or other so that the participants can also have access and write in their responses in real-time.

TIPS**HOW**

The CoP moderator prepares a project related issue or asks one of the participants to prepare an issue to share with the group. Then the other participants are asked to think of a set of questions that need to be answered to tackle the problem. The CoP moderator will write the issue and the questions on a flipchart or online program and a discussion will follow in which the group discusses the issue and tries to answer the questions identified. The discussion will end with a brief reflection in which the moderator asks the group for their main conclusions and looks ahead by trying to answer the questions:

- 1) Who is needed to address these problems?
- 2) What obstacles are expected?
- 3) How the participants can support each other? (Dosière & Wilems, 2016).

The moderator must also ensure that all participants can share freely and in a respectful way by creating a safe space and environment.

MATERIALS NEEDED

- Flipchart
- Pen
- Online meeting platform

MODERATION TECHNIQUE

Lego with Pestle bias

WHAT

This method aims to sort the challenges, risks and solutions into two categories that can be categorised even further. This method is the first step to do so.

HOW

The CoP moderator prepares a table with Lego blocks and in the centre of the table a piece of paper with a statement, question or topic of relevance within the case study. The CoP participants are asked to write down the risks and the solutions to manage these risks on post-its in two different colours. The post-its should be attached to the Lego pieces (Freitas et al.,2018).

BENEFITS

- Method supports active participation of all participants
- Find solutions/ideas for tackling the issues
- Supports out of the box thinking
- Fun method
- Helps visualising challenges and potential solutions
- Facilitates uncovering assumptions and positions
- Supports discussion and learning from other perspectives.

TIPS

ONLINE TIP

This method could be converted online, whereby the CoP moderator can set up via an online program such as Mural or Google Slides a virtual lego table (i.e. draw it or design it with elements within these online tools), where participants can click, drag and type on online post-its/text boxes. The discussion can be carried out within the online meeting platform and also via the chat function and notes and outcomes can be taken simultaneously, and screenshots saved of the outcome.

MATERIALS NEEDED

- Flipchart
- Pen
- Online meetingplatform

MODERATION TECHNIQUE

Mapping spots

WHAT

This method allows the CoP participants to identify critical places/points in the case studies.

BENEFITS

- Generates a quick overview of the risk and different opinions
- Fun exercise
- Creates a visual overview
- Supports discussion and prioritisation

HOW

A big map of the case study can be placed on a wall/ table/online program. The participants are asked to write down the most urgent risks for specific locations on red post-its, and places with almost no risks on green post-its, and places that they use a lot on yellow post-its and place them on the map. This gives a visual overview of where the main risks lie according to the participants. Then the participants are invited to discuss the various identified risks as the participants might have different opinions and to find solutions and ways forward (Freitas et al., 2018).

ONLINE TIP

This exercise can be done online as well using an online tool such as Mural, Whiteboard or Google Slides, and using a picture of the area as background. Then the participants can use pre-defined text boxes to add in their high, low, frequently used coloured post-its and discussion can ensue via an online meeting program.

MATERIALS NEEDED

- Map in A0 size
 - Green, yellow and red post-its
 - Pens
 - Mural/GroupMap
-

TIPS

MODERATION TECHNIQUE

SWOT world café

WHAT

The SWOT world café allows participants to jointly map the strengths, weaknesses, opportunities and threats with regards to a specific project, which can be used as a basis foundation for more in depth discussion and action planning (Freitas et al.,2018).

BENEFITS

- Supports participation of all participants
- Allows for a relatively fast SWOT analysis
- Supports informal knowledge exchange
- Supports reflection
- Allows for different perspectives

TIPS**ONLINE TIP**

This method can be done online as well using a meeting platform which offers breakout sessions such as Zoom, in combination with an online program such as Mural, Padlet, GroupMap or Google Slides.

HOW

There are four different tables placed in a room. Each of the tables is dedicated to one category of the SWOT analysis; the strengths, weaknesses, opportunities and threats.

On each table, there is a A0 paper. The CoP participants are divided in equal groups around each table and have 15 minutes for discussion on the specific SWOT dimension of the table. Each table has a table moderator which can take notes on the post-its and put them on the paper and cluster the post-its as needed.

After 15 minutes, the participants move to the next table, so that each group has visited each table. The posters are put on the wall so that the participants can review the posters and there can be a brief open discussion.

Then, the participants are invited to select the 5 most important points in each dimension. They are invited to put a sticker on these post-its as a vote. After everyone has done so, there will be a more in-depth public discussion on the selected points per dimension to enable further planning and coordination.

MATERIALS NEEDED

- Tables
- A0 paper
- Pens
- Post-its
- Online meeting platform

MODERATION TECHNIQUE

Influence and motivation matrix

WHAT

The influence and motivation matrix is an icebreaker exercise and aims to understand how participants view themselves and others (Freitas et al., 2018).

HOW

The CoP moderator prepares a poster (A0 size) on which a stakeholder matrix is drawn. On the x-axis is the level of motivation of the participants and on the y-axis is their influence. The participants all receive a post-it and are asked to write their name on it. Then the participants are asked to put their post-it on the motivation matrix where they perceive themselves. The other participants can give feedback on the placement of names. This can be done for various thematic topics. The CoP moderator is in charge of analysing the motivation/influence matrix (Freitas et al., 2018).

BENEFITS

- Allows the participants to introduce themselves and to get to know power dynamics and interests

ONLINE TIP

This method can be used online as well using an online tool such as Mural, Whiteboard or Google Slides.

CONS

- Time consuming in larger groups

MATERIALS NEEDED

- A0 paper
- Pens
- Post-its
- Online meeting platform

MODERATION TECHNIQUE

“Futuribles” storytelling role play

WHAT

This method aims to map the expectations of the project outcomes and to create understanding for each other's point of view.

BENEFITS

- Fun and interactive
- Helps the creation of common ground between the participants
- Facilitates expectation management

TIPS

ONLINE TIP

This activity can be done online with an online meeting tool that enables breakout rooms.

MATERIALS NEEDED

-
- Enough time and space to perform the sketches
 - Online meeting tool with breakout rooms

HOW

The participants are divided into groups and are asked to collaboratively envision the outcomes of the project. The groups are asked to role play situations and to plan performances to play out to the other participants: a TV interview after the project has ended OR a project meeting of a new project after this project has ended. The participants in the groups have to prepare their story and roles (Freitas et al., 2018).

In the TV-interview scenario the participants have to prepare the questions that the interviewer will ask and their answers to it. This is all done jointly, once the group agrees on the answers and questions the roles to play are divided. The two groups both perform their sketches. After the performances the group can discuss the differences and overlap between the expected outcomes of the project and try to come to a joint agreement.

Moderation techniques for defining the scope and direction

These moderation techniques help the participants plan and define their course of action.

Overview

- a. [Backcasting](#)
- b. [Roadmap design](#)

MODERATION TECHNIQUE

Backcasting

WHAT

This method can be used to envision the direction of the project and identify challenges and help planning (Freitas et al., 2018)

BENEFITS

- Enables visualising the main challenges and steps needed
- Raises awareness
- Contextual
- Helps the participants to plan ahead

ONLINE TIP

This method can also be used online, for example by using Mural or GroupMap. However, for the discussion in small groups, breakout sessions are needed, therefore a meeting platform such as Zoom or other with breakout room capacity should be used.

HOW

The participants are asked to think of their nightmare and dream scenarios. On a poster, a timeline is drawn and the participants are handed post-its and pens. They are asked to write on the post-its key events or topics that lead to the dream or nightmare scenarios. This identifies challenges that need to be addressed.

After noted on the poster, the participants are divided in groups to work on specific topics. They are asked to discuss what needs to happen to stay away from the nightmare scenario and move towards the dream scenario. The participants are asked to put the steps on a timeline.

Afterwards, there will be a group discussion in which the participants share their main issues and actions to be taken to move towards the dream scenario (Freitas et al., 2018).

MATERIALS NEEDED

- Posters
 - Pens
 - Post-its
-

MODERATION TECHNIQUE

Roadmap design

WHAT

Participants design a collective roadmap with actions for successful implementation of the project.

BENEFITS

- Enables the formulation of concrete ideas and action
- Interactive method for planning

ONLINE TIP

This method can also be used online, but requires a meeting platform that offers breakout sessions such as Zoom. Note-taking and brainstorming can be done via an online tool such as Mural, GroupMap or Google Slides.

HOW

The CoP participants are divided into groups and are asked to design a roadmap with concrete actions that would lead to implementation and success for the project. This can be implementation in the project, in the case study site or in the political agenda.

Once the groups have finished their roadmaps they are put on a wall and the group as a whole can discuss the various solutions and actions. The CoP moderator ends the discussion by providing an overview of the common identified issues and easiest ways to take action (Freitas et al., 2018).

MATERIALS NEEDED

- Posters
 - Pens
 - Post-its
-

Moderation techniques for brainstorming

These techniques facilitate discussion and brainstorming sessions.

Overview

- a. [Roundtables](#)
- b. [The other way around](#)
- c. [Quick scan ideas rope](#)
- d. [The world café setting](#)

MODERATION TECHNIQUE

Roundtable

WHAT

Participants discuss topics separated by tables / spaces, and synthesize all of the input as a group.

BENEFITS

- Supports active participation on all the issues.
- Supports building on ideas of others
- Allows input from all participants
- Facilitates knowledge exchange

ONLINE TIP

This method can also be used online. A meeting platform that has breakout rooms/sessions should be used, such as Zoom.

HOW

In a room with tables, the moderator assigns a different topic to each table with several questions prepared per topic. A table moderator is assigned to take notes.

The CoP participants are divided in equal groups around the tables. At each table, the group has 10-15 minutes to discuss the topic at hand and then move to the next table. The table moderator summarises the main discussion points of the previous groups. Then the new group has time to discuss and at the end of the 15 minutes. When every group has visited each table the table moderators publicly give a synthesis of what has been discussed at their table followed by a brief discussion (Freitas et al., 2018).

MATERIALS NEEDED

- Tables
 - A0 paper
 - Pens
 - Post-its
-

MODERATION TECHNIQUE

The other way around

WHAT

Participants think about worst possible outcomes, and then work backwards from there to find solutions.

BENEFITS

- Helps breaking out of fixed thinking patterns
- Stimulates innovative thinking
- Interactive method

ONLINE TIP

This method can be used online as well. If the participants are split into small groups, a platform that allows breakout sessions should be used, such as Zoom. Note-taking can be done by sharing screens and/or using an online tool that all participants can access in real-time such as Mural, GroupMap or Google Slides.

HOW

The participants are given a challenge and instead of asking them to come up with solutions, they are asked to think about how to make the problem worse. The participants are divided in groups of 2-3 people and are given five minutes to write down their ideas. The CoP moderator divides a poster in two sections and will ask the participants to briefly present their ideas, while the moderator notes down the ideas on the left side of the poster. Once all the ideas are written down, the group collectively thinks of how the ideas to make the situation worse, can be translated into solutions to improve the current situation (Dirkse-Hulscher & Talen, 2007).

MATERIALS NEEDED

-
- Flipchart
 - Pen

TIPS

MODERATION TECHNIQUE

Quick-scan ideas rope

WHAT

Participants capture and share ideas that might not be immediately relevant and hang them on a physical or virtual rope for later use and discussion.

BENEFITS

- Prevents the loss of ideas and insights
- Easy way to share knowledge and ideas

ONLINE TIP

This activity can also be held online. This can be done using an online meeting program, such as Zoom or MS Teams. A digital rope can be created by using an online program or application (such as Mural, Whiteboard, GroupMap or Mentimeter wordcloud) that allows people to type or post their ideas to be share at the end of the meeting.

TIPS

HOW

During the CoP an “idea rope” can be hung around the room where CoP participants can hang up their ideas that occur during the meeting, which might not be immediately relevant for the immediate discussion, but could be interesting for the other participants (Freitas et al., 2018).

The CoP moderator should collect the ideas at the end of the session and make them available for all the participants afterwards.

MATERIALS NEEDED

-
- Rope
 - Paper
 - Pens
 - Clips

MODERATION TECHNIQUE

The world café setting

WHAT

Participants discuss pre-defined topics at separate tables and switch tables after a predetermined time. After a few table switches, there is a plenary discussion to share ideas.

BENEFITS

- Allows for discussing complex issues in larger groups
- Allows for all participants to participate even in bigger groups
- Facilitates knowledge exchange in an informal atmosphere
- Facilitates fast collection of knowledge
- Multiple issues/ topics can be discussed in the same session (UNICEF, 2015)

ONLINE TIP

This method can be used online using a platform that offers breakout sessions such as Zoom, and with an online note-taking tool.

TIPS

HOW

Before the CoP meeting, the CoP moderator selects a topic and designs 3-5 discussion topics/questions and selects a table host and a table reporter per topic. In the meeting room, a table per topic will be set up accompanied by a flipchart. During the session, the CoP participants are divided evenly over the various tables. The table hosts and reporters remain at their table the whole session of the world café. Each round starts with a brief explanation on the topic by the table host and a brief summary of the discussion of the previous group at that table.

After the introduction and the recap, the discussion of 20 minutes can begin in which the participants write down their ideas. Only the ideas that they shared with the group should be written down. When the 20 minutes are over, the groups switch tables. Once all groups have visited all tables, there will be a plenary reflection in which the table host summarises the findings from each table and a brief discussion will follow (UNICEF, 2015). The CoP moderator ends the session with a conclusion.

MATERIALS NEEDED

- Table host and reporter
 - Flipchart
 - Pens
-

Moderation techniques for making knowledge explicit

This method helps to make implicit knowledge explicit and facilitates exchange.

Overview

- a. Expert knowledge

MODERATION TECHNIQUE

Expert Knowledge

WHAT

Expert knowledge is a method to facilitate implicit knowledge exchange by making it explicit.

BENEFITS

- Interactive
- Allows to make implicit knowledge explicit

ONLINE TIP

Can be done through polling tool, such as Mentimeter or Slido, or through the integrate polling in Zoom.

TIPS

MATERIALS NEEDED

- Room with enough space

HOW

To use this method, it is necessary that the CoP participants are familiar with the topic of discussion. If deemed necessary, the CoP moderator can ask the participants to prepare before the meeting.

The CoP moderator prepares questions for the group which match their knowledge on the topic. During the session the CoP moderator will introduce the topic and divide the room in two sections. One for true and one for false. The CoP moderator will provide statements and the participants have to answer to these statement by standing in either the true or false section.

Once everyone stands in their section, the CoP moderator will ask the participants to explain their answer. If the moderator notices that the explanation is not correct, they will interrupt the participant and give the right answer with explicit explanation.

This exercise is not about having a discussion, but about highlighting how implicit information can be made explicit with an activity, and helping people to retain information through active engagement.

Moderation techniques for decision making

These methods help the participants in a CoP to reach consensus and to make decisions. Towards the end of the project, decisions must be made and thus consensus and agreement will be sought. The following moderation techniques can facilitate these decision-making processes.

Overview

- a. Perspectives
- b. Personas
- c. Scenarios

MODERATION TECHNIQUE

Perspectives

WHAT

Perspectives moderation is like role-playing. Participants take on assigned roles, brainstorm ideas, and share them with the group.

BENEFITS

- Creates more understanding of others perspectives
- Helps to reach decisions and consensus

ONLINE TIP

This exercise can also be done online a platform with breakout, such as through Zoom. Online note taking and voting can be done through an online program such as Mural, GroupMap or Whiteboard.

TIPS**HOW**

The CoP moderator writes down all possible decisions on the flipchart and all stakeholder groups (which are participating in the CoP) on cards. The cards are then divided over the CoP participants to enable participants to take on each other's roles and perspectives. The CoP moderator makes sure that no one receives their own role.

The participants with the same cards form groups and brainstorm arguments for why a specific decision should be taken. After some time, everyone comes back to the main group and the participants must present their arguments for the decision with their assigned role.

After this discussion, everyone switches back to their own role and perspectives and a new discussion will start. During the discussions, the CoP moderator writes down the arguments and solutions that have come up to proceed with a specific decision. At the end of the discussion the CoP moderator will ask the participants to vote for one of the solutions (Dirkse-Hulscher & Talen, 2007).

MATERIALS NEEDED

- Cards with roles
- Pens
- Flipchart or whiteboard

MODERATION TECHNIQUE

Personas

WHAT

This method stimulates the participants to step out of their own perspectives and to create more understanding for others' perspectives and jointly identify drivers and barriers for collective action (Freitas et al., 2018).

HOW

The group maps all relevant stakeholders in the context of their project/issue. The group then divides the personas of the different stakeholders among the group. The CoP participants with the same persona are asked to develop a profile of this persona with their perceptions of the issue at hand.

BENEFITS

- The participants are forced to think from different perspectives
- Identifies the drivers and barriers
- Enhances mutual understanding

The groups then share their developed persona profiles with the group and the group is asked to discuss the drivers and barriers for joint action based on the profiles (Freitas et al., 2018). The CoP moderator writes down the identified drivers and barriers for collective action.

ONLINE TIP

This method can be used online as well if a meeting platform with breakout sessions is used, such as Zoom. Online note taking can be done with an online program such as Mural, GroupMap, WhiteBoard or Google Slides with a shared screen.

MATERIALS NEEDED

- Poster
 - Pens
 - Markers
-

TIPS

MODERATION TECHNIQUE

Scenarios

WHAT

The scenarios method is used to reach consensus between a wide range of stakeholders and to come to a well informed decision (Dirkse-Hulscher & Talen, 2007).

HOW

During the CoP meeting there will be a discussion which aims to come up with a list of possible solutions or decisions.

The CoP moderator writes down the solutions/decisions on a flipchart or whiteboard. The group is divided into small groups. Each group is assigned a solution or decision. In these smaller groups the participants are asked to list the positive and negative consequences of each solution/decision and the effects on the involved stakeholders.

The groups are then asked to identify the consequences with the biggest impacts and are asked to think of ways to lower the impact. In this way, scenarios are formulated. The group comes together again and the CoP moderator will note down all the identified consequences of the solutions/decisions on a poster or flipchart. Based on this overview, the group can vote for a decision (Dirkse-Hulscher & Talen, 2007).

BENEFITS

- Quick overview of the consequences of solutions
- Helps to reach consensus between the CoP participants
- Helps to come to a joint decision

ONLINE TIP

This method can also be used online if a meeting platform which offers breakout sessions such as Zoom. Note-taking and presenting the ideas can be done via a PowerPoint on the shared screen, or with an online tool such as Mural, Whiteboard, Google Slides, etc.

TIPS**MATERIALS NEEDED**

- Flipchart, whiteboard
- Pen

Annex 3: Stakeholder distribution by type and role/profile, per LL

Annex 5: Evaluation form

This form will be slightly adjusted to the specificities of the project when made on-line.

Location: _____ **Date:** _____

It was a pleasure to have you in this meeting. We would like to know your opinion, so that we can improve future events and meet your expectations. Thank you for your collaboration!

Name (*optional*): _____

Organisation (*optional*): _____

Organisation Support

The **Evaluation form** will be made available online by **KWR**.

Please rate the extent to which you agree with each of the following statements:
(1=strongly disagree; 2=disagree 3=neutral; 4=agree; 5=strongly agree; N.A.=not applicable)

1. Meeting logistics and stakeholder engagement	
1.1 I received the information about the meeting and materials well in advance	
1.2 The venue was adequate for the purpose of the meeting	
1.3 The meeting had the right duration in time ²	
1.4 During the meeting I improved or made new connections for my professional network	
1.5 The presentations and speakers were clear and understandable	
1.6 During the meeting, I felt save to behave spontaneous and unfiltered	
1.7 I believe others were communicating openly with me	
Comments: (<i>optional</i>)	
2. Awareness and increased understanding	
2.1 I believe that all relevant stakeholders were present at the meeting	
2.2 I had sufficient opportunities to provide input to the discussion	
2.3 Differences and (potential) conflicts among us were addressed in a constructive manner	
2.4 All ideas/perspectives were included and respected during the discussion	
2.5 I feel that the right topics were discussed during the meeting	
2.6 I have a better understanding of the perspective of the stakeholders	
2.7 The way the discussion was facilitated and moderated supported the meeting objectives	

² “Strongly disagree” means you found the meeting too short or too long and “strongly agree” means you found the duration of the meeting fully adequate. If you need to add a more detailed evaluation, please use the box “comments” below.

Comments: *(optional)*

3. Outcomes and conclusions

3.1 There was enough time to reflect on our collective experience and functioning as a group

3.2 I believe that clear conclusions were formulated at the end of the meeting

3.3 I believe that clear actions were formulated to improve solutions

3.4 The meeting inspired me to take follow-up actions in my own organisation

3.5 Participating in the meeting increased my knowledge on the solutions

3.6 My expectations on the outcomes of the meeting were met

3.7 I am aware of my own role in the project and how each of us can contribute to the project's goals

Comments: *(optional)*

Pros and cons of the local CoP

What is your overall rating of the CoP meeting (1 to 5)?

In your opinion, what were the most positive and less positive aspects of the meeting?

Most positive:

Less positive:

Suggestions for improvement

What suggestions for improvement do you have for future meetings?

Thanks!

Please give this questionnaire back to the workshop organizer before leaving.

Annex 6: Template for CoP meeting reporting

CoP Meeting Report

The CoP Coordinator is responsible to prepare and share a CoP Meeting Report after each CoP meeting.

Title of CoP Meeting (key topic):

- Organizing partner:
- Moderator:
- Meeting Place:
- Date:
- Number of guests attending:

Agenda for the meeting

- Please insert the agenda of your meeting

Objectives

- Describe the CoP meeting objectives

Participants' characterization

- Table below shows the number of participants, the respective sector of activity and the level of governance in which each stakeholder is active.

Overview of stakeholders:

Institution / sector	No. of participants (registrations)			
	In total	Male	Female	Non-binary
Project members				
External stakeholders (outside of the project partners)				
Authorities				
Engineering companies				
Representatives of other sectors				
Research institute				
End-users				
Water industry				
Other: name				

Please, include a list of participants as annex to this form.

Description of meeting's activities

- Provide a summary of activities carried out. Were there plenary or working group sessions? Presentations by whom on what? (Provide presentations as appendices).
- Describe the moderation technique and method for open dialogue applied.

Please, include all presentations given at the meeting as annex to this form.

Main achievements

- Describe briefly the main outcomes and results from the meeting, including the answers on the central questions such as outlined in Section 4.1 'Key topics of CoP meetings', as well as any actions to be taken by members, as agreed upon.
- Summarise the perspectives of the stakeholders (i.e., stories as anecdotal evidence).

Reflection notes

- Describe your observations on stakeholder engagement (e.g., do we need to add others?)
- Describe any relevant observations for further steps
- Questions such as below can be asked:
 - What did you enjoy most/less about this workshop?
 - Which methods/tools were successful/not successful?

In your opinion, what were the positive/negative aspects of the workshop?

Pros:

- XXX
- XXX
- XXX

Cons:

- XXX
- XXX
- XXX

What suggestions for improvement do you have for future workshops?

- XXX
- XXX
- XXX

Annex 7: Suggestions for designing a Protocol for CoP operation

During the first CoP Meeting, it is important to co-define with the stakeholders how the community will operate, to ensure a bottom-up approach and gain consensus on the community’s approach. This Annex provides some high-level ideas to help LL owners and mentors, and CoP Coordinators develop a draft protocol of rules and procedures for the operation of their CoP.

During the first CoP Meeting, as seen in the CoP Guidance Document, there are many key questions to cover with the stakeholders. These could take quite a while to decide on as a group, so it is important to go to the first meeting with already a draft document on how to operate the community. You can then discuss your proposal with stakeholders. Input from stakeholders can be gathered via an online tool, such as GroupMap or polling tool like Mentimeter, or you can do a simple raise of hands with cameras on. For in-person meetings, this can be done by a show of hands.

The table below is the same presented as Table 2: First CoP Meeting Template in section 2.3.1, now with included high-level tips and suggestions for the meeting. Note that you do not have to go through all the questions listed in the “Middle” section below, but they are just there to support you in finding the best way to operate the community with input from the participants. You can pick and choose 2-3 questions that work best for you to also limit the duration of the meeting.

Beginning
<p>Greeting and Introduction</p> <p>Explanation of meeting logistics and agenda (online or in-person)</p> <p>In case of online meetings, remind the participants that the meeting is going to be recorded (provided consent was given previously)</p> <p>Round of introductions with stakeholders and CoP Coordinator and Moderator</p>
Beginning
<p>Greeting and Introduction</p> <p>Explanation of meeting logistics and agenda (online or in-person)</p> <p>In case of online meetings, remind the participants that the meeting is going to be recorded</p> <p>Round of introductions with stakeholders and CoP Coordinator and Moderator</p>
Middle
<p>Validate pre-identified objectives, mission and ambition (or vision) of CoP with the stakeholders – refine together to ensure that these are aligned with the stakeholders’ expectations. Working towards a shared objective/vision is critical to community development.</p> <p>Questions to be answered by the stakeholders are:</p>

- What topics and issues do we really care about?
- What are the development challenges we want to address?
- What outcomes do we want to focus on?
- What is out of scope?
- How is this domain connected to the organisation's strategy?
- What is in it for us?
- What kind of influence do we want to have?
- How will we communicate the community's goals and achievements, and to whom?

The answers to these questions will help a community to develop a shared understanding of its objective, find its legitimacy in the organisation and engage the passion of its members (Brouwer et al., 2018).

These topics are particularly important to discuss as a group. You can send these out ahead of the meeting for stakeholders to think about prior to the meeting, as well as prepare an online tool, like GroupMap, to capture their responses and have an easier time to collect information and summarize. You should also predefine as the CoP Coordinator and LL what the specific topics for your CoP might be and enable a vote among the community, and if anything is missing.

***Co-define the specific ways the community will operate**, build relationships and grow. Establish the operating practice and knowledge system, as seen with example questions below (Brouwer et al., 2018):

Goals: Find the community's specific way to operate, build relationships, and grow.

- How will the community be organized and run?
- Is membership open, closed or something in between?
- What roles are members going to play?
- How will decisions be made?
- How often will the community meet?
- What kind of activities will generate energy and develop trust?
- What kind of behaviors can we expect from each other (respect, honest feedback, etc.)?
- How can the community balance the needs of various segments of members?

*** Key suggestions for each question can be found below this table**

Co-define the short and long-term value for the organisations and attending stakeholders, in connection with the identified needs and desired outcomes of the CoP. **This can be done with reflection and/or a survey during the meeting.** The Value Matrix in Table 1 can be used to identify shared values of the CoP (Koti et al., 2017)

****Co-design the community in a way that it becomes an effective knowledge resource** for its members. Consider addressing the following questions in your first meeting.

- How will community actions result in outcomes?
- What knowledge to share, develop, document?
- What kinds of learning activities to organize?
- How should we use collective learning, versus expert-apprentice, versus external research/expertise?
- What potential work groups could be created?
- Where are the sources of knowledge and benchmarks outside the community?
- How should we support members as both experts and learners?
- What are the benefits for members?

**** Key suggestions for each question can be found below this table**

Map out the most important stakeholders and to fill any gaps in terms of involvement of a particular organisation or person. Also discuss and consider the interest and power relations of stakeholders openly in a constructive and respectful manner, discussing the in a way that enables everyone to share their perspective and willingness to contribute. Should any stakeholders not wish to take part as a result of disagreement or lack of interest, find a mutually beneficial way to uphold the relationship even with minor or no involvement in the CoP (i.e., through period email correspondence, one-on-one discussions with some of the partners, etc.).

Key suggestions: We recommend sharing the stakeholder mapping done for your Living Lab CoP (without contact information) with the participants ahead of the meeting. Then during the meeting, you can ask them if they identified any gaps or issues and have a discussion period on this. By using an online tool, you can capture any names of missing stakeholders.

End

Summarise the discussions into a **Community Charter**, which will be agreed upon by all stakeholders involved in the CoP during this first meeting. Once it has been drafted and finalized, send around to all CoP Members, which will finalise the long-term design and accountability to the CoP (Koti et al., 2017)

Share any relevant documents or links to meeting evaluation – reserve time during the meeting for this and send after in a summary email.

Summarise meeting and define next steps together as a group.

***Co-define the specific ways the community will operate**, build relationships and grow. Establish the operating practice and knowledge system, as seen with example questions below (Brouwer et al., 2018):

Goals: Find the community's specific way to operate, build relationships, and grow.

<p>How will the community be organized and run?</p>	<p>Considerations: How will the community communicate in-between meetings (e.g., emails, newsletters, online space, WhatsApp Group?), how will notes and meeting summaries be shared? Where will the community meet? Online? Which tool will be used?</p> <p>We recommend: Keeping in touch with emails or an online space decided on by the group, sending out frequent email updates about the Living Lab developments.</p>
<p>Is membership open, closed or something in between?</p>	<p>Considerations: Stakeholders are invited to join the CoP at the beginning of the project. During the 1st CoP meeting, you can decide together if any stakeholders are missing, and whether or not you might like involvement from outside the stakeholder group. Or should it be completely closed off to just those who have accepted?</p> <p>We recommend: To keep CoP fairly closed off, to ensure ease of operation. Should an external speaker wish to be invited, that can be of course an option. However, there should also be some flexibility given the nature of the projects and Living Labs where stakeholders might change and need to be replaced.</p>
<p>What roles are members going to play?</p>	<p>Considerations: Here is where you can define together the involvement stakeholders of the CoP. Keep in mind that different stakeholders will have different levels of engagement, and some may be more proactive than others, and some may be more extroverted or vocal than others.</p> <p>We recommend: We recommend that some stakeholders can take over some responsibilities during the meetings, such as note-taking or supporting in the preparation of email updates, newsletters, etc. Stakeholder can also be asked to keep the community alive in between meetings and to send periodic updates. They can also simply decide to just attend each of the meetings.</p>
<p>How will decisions be made?</p>	<p>Considerations: What type of governance style will the CoP have? Who will make decisions? Is it a majority vote or other methods?</p> <p>We recommend: We recommend enabling a bottom-up approach as much as possible, and to enable constant feedback and decision-making from the community. This can be managed by having time during each meeting to make decisions by voting and using the majority vote rule. Keep in mind how to manage those who disagree.</p>
<p>How often will the community meet?</p>	<p>Considerations: Think about how many times per year you would like to meet, once or twice per year? Will there be focus-group meetings on specific sub-topics?</p> <p>We recommend: 1-2 meetings per year, with potential room for focus group meetings on more technical or specific topics that should only be discussed with a key sub-group of stakeholders. Meetings with all stakeholders should have more cross-cutting themes and issues.</p>

<p>What kind of activities will generate energy and develop trust?</p>	<p>Considerations: This is important to ensure the appropriate dynamics between members and levels of engagement. Also, to ensure that any information or opinions shared can be well-received by the community.</p> <p>We recommend: We recommend ensuring some form of informal activities during the meetings or in-between meetings to make sure the community can build relationships and trust among each other. Fun activities, games or ice-breaking activities to get to know each other better are effective.</p>
<p>What kind of behaviours can we expect from each other (respect, honest feedback, etc.)?</p>	<p>Considerations: Consider key values you hope to establish in your CoP (e.g., teamwork, professionalism, sharing, feedback, trust, respect, etc.).</p> <p>We recommend: Thinking of these values ahead of time, and then using a WordCloud tool, such as Mentimeter, you can take 5 minutes to ask everyone to share 2-3 words that represent different values and behaviours they expect in the group. Then you can see which words are more prominent and have a discussion on these. Gather the terms and add them into the report and Community Charter to be shared and validated after the first CoP Meeting.</p>
<p>How can the community balance the needs of various segments of members?</p>	<p>Considerations: Consider all the different kinds of stakeholders and experts you have in the room and how this might affect the working and sharing culture of the CoP. Some might be more senior than others, some might be more technical, business oriented, etc.</p> <p>We recommend: Make these differences explicit to the members through an activity such as from the moderation techniques in the Annex of the guidance document (e.g., a role-playing activity). Then you are helping the participants to better understand each other and put each other in their own shoes. After such an activity, you can then have an open discussion about this topic, as well as capture ideas in an online tool such as GroupMap. This can also be linked to the question below in the “Effective Knowledge Resource” section on: “What potential work groups could be created?” – Perhaps to balance the needs of all the different stakeholders you can form “Focus Groups” and hold separate meetings on more focused/specific/technical topics with a subset of the community, reporting back to the entire community later on.</p>
<p>**Co-design the community in a way that it becomes an effective knowledge resource for its members. Consider addressing the following questions in your first meeting.</p>	
<p>How will community actions result in outcomes?</p>	<p>Considerations: In your roadmap planning of the CoP Meetings, this is an important element to consider, and to share your initial thoughts with the participants to get their feedback.</p> <p>We recommend: Sharing your several ideas of which outcomes you want the CoP to achieve, and which agreeing on which actions or methods will achieve those. This can be done with a mapping exercise, in a group discussion, in breakout rooms on each specific topic. You can look at the 2 moderation techniques in the Annex under “Moderation techniques for defining the scope and direction”.</p>

<p>What knowledge to share, develop, document?</p>	<p>Considerations: Similar to the above question, this is something you should pre-prepare in your CoP Roadmap planning, having an idea of your specific Living Lab and what you want to achieve with the participants, and then verifying those ideas with the participants.</p> <p>We recommend: Highlighting your suggestions and using an online tool to enable further comments and ideas to come about based on your participants' feedback. This could be through GroupMap, WhiteBoard, etc.</p>
<p>What kinds of learning activities to organize?</p>	<p>Considerations: It is also important to define some ideas before the meeting, such as webinars, inviting guest speakers to the meeting, newsletter, etc. and asking the group to vote on the ones that are best suited for them. Consider what the best ways are for each of your stakeholders to create and uptake knowledge.</p> <p>We recommend: Show your ideas to the group and have an opportunity to ask for other suggestions and then vote on 2-3 to manage the scope and capacity of the CoP.</p>
<p>How should we use collective learning, versus expert-apprentice, versus external research/expertise?</p>	<p>Considerations: Similar to the previous question, but here it is more specific in how the learning activities would take place between the different types of stakeholders you have. You can propose these types of learning to your participants and see if these are methods they would like to use.</p> <p>We recommend: Discuss this during the meeting, by connecting it with the question in the previous section on “How can the community balance the needs of various segments of members?” – after the role-playing and understanding your stakeholders, you may have a better idea of how many different types of experts you have and which activities they may enjoy, such as: senior to junior learning opportunities and meetings, collective learning as a group, and inviting in external researchers and/or experts on a topic you decide to discuss during your meetings along the roadmap.</p> <p>This is also related to planning the number of meetings you want to have, as seen in the previous section.</p>
<p>What potential work groups could be created?</p>	<p>See previous questions on How many meetings to have? And How can the community balance the needs of various segments of members?</p>
<p>Where are the sources of knowledge and benchmarks outside the community?</p>	<p>Considerations: This is a good way to capture any existing knowledge and expertise in the sector, from reports to experts outside of the project and Living Lab.</p> <p>We recommend: Capturing ideas in an online tool which you can ask people to do ahead of the meeting to save time. Then you can look at the GroupMap or Survey tool during the meeting. The CoP Coordinator can then compile all the ideas and create a repository. The experts and resources can also be considered to be invited to CoP meetings or focus group meetings depending on the group's desires.</p>
<p>How should we support members</p>	<p>Considerations: Enabling experts to share and learn, enable a culture of learning, feedback and trust.</p>

<p>as both experts and learners?</p>	<p>We recommend: Use moderation techniques that enable people to serve in both roles, ensure safe and trusting spaces to share and discuss. Propose ideas and share with the group and gather their feedback in a discussion and/or online tool like GroupMap.</p>
<p>What are the benefits for members?</p>	<p>Considerations: This can be built off based on the Value Matrix Table, as well as any other benefits you see that members get from participating in the CoP.</p> <p>We recommend: You can also ask participants to think about this themselves ahead of the meeting, to gather their expectations and to try and fulfill them during the meeting. Then you can ask the members similar questions in a post-meeting survey and see if they identified any others after participating in the first meeting.</p>

Annex 8: Consent forms

B-WaterSmart: Accelerating Water Smartness in Coastal Europe Communities of Practice (CoP)

Information sheet

B-WaterSmart is a 4-year Project funded by the European Commission (Horizon 2020, GA no. 869171) which will be developed until August 2024. It aims at enabling water-smart systems, societies and economies that are more resilient to climate change impacts and supportive of a thriving European water-dependent business. The Project consortium brings together six coastal European cities and regions as Living Labs - Alicante, Bodø, Flanders, Lisbon, East Frisia, and Venice - in a large-scale systemic approach to select, connect and demonstrate tailored suites of innovative technology, management, and interoperable smart data solutions for multiple users and sectors. The systemic innovation approach is based on the co-creation of solutions by '**Communities of Practice**' (**CoP**) and a joint 'Innovation Alliance' (INALL) of problem-owners; it builds on collaborative work with citizens, institutions, non-governmental organisations and businesses, with the common objective of developing solutions for societal, regulatory and governance issues, and supporting methodologies to enable systemic innovation for water-smartness, and capacity building.

You are been invited to join this B-WaterSmart CoP as representative of a key sector that is fundamental for developing innovative solutions for water management in [insert your region/city], towards a model of Circular Economy that makes the most of the available environmental resources and avoids waste as much as possible. It is therefore very important for the Project team to get to know your opinion on the current state of water management and the related policies and legislation. We will be organising group discussions to collect information on the main concerns, proposals and ideas of the representatives of this sector, including public institutions, businesses and sectoral associations, and also especially your opinions on the type of technological and digital solutions that B-WaterSmart is developing.

The information collected (sound and video recordings, written notes) will only be used by the Project research team (members of the consortium), will be kept confidential and not transmitted to third parties. Data will be anonymised previous to their analysis and will be stored in computers and servers protected by passwords, only accessible by the members of the research team directly involved in the organisation and accompaniment of the CoP. After anonymised and analysed, the information collected might be used for the purposes of communicating and disseminating the Project results, through research publications (scientific journals), communications in conferences and other events (see consent form below). However, the opinions expressed will not be directly identified, meaning that they will not be traced back to each person. The data will be stored only for as long as they are necessarily to carry these analyses, and no data will be kept beyond the end of the Project (August 2024).

There will be at least one meeting like this per year, in each of the cities/regions involved in B-WaterSmart, and participation is free of any kind of material compensation. We anticipate that this meeting will take approximately [two hours], during which there will be a [pause for coffee]. We are thankful for your participation and hope that you will find this debate useful and engaging!

Should you need more information on the local activities of the project or any clarification regarding the use of data generated during CoP activities, please feel free to contact the CoP Coordinator at any time:

[Insert contact details of CoP Coordinator]

In the case you need more information on the overall project contents and its approach or to issue a complaint regarding the use of your data in this project, you can contact the project coordination team:

David Schwesig (d.schwesid@iww-online.de)
 Kristina Wencki (k.wencki@iww-online.de)

You can withdraw your participation at any time and request access to your personal data and information, as well as request them to be deleted should you wish so, through the mentioned contacts. There is no consequence if you decide to give up, and you don't need to provide any reason why.

In fulfillment of the EU General Data Protection Regulation (GDPR, 2016/679), the B-WaterSmart team kindly requests your confirmation and permission for the following:

Informed consent form

	YES	NO
I have understood the objectives of this research and they were adequately explained to me, in a language and in terms I can fully understand.		
I had the opportunity to ask questions and clarify any doubts.		
I have voluntarily accepted to participate in the CoP discussion groups and join the activities proposed during this event.		
I understand that I can withdraw my participation at any time, as well as request my personal data and information to be deleted, without any consequences or having to give any specific reason for that.		
I understand that I can refuse to answer and to give my opinions on any topic if I don't want to.		
I understand that my personal data – name, employer, phone number(s), email address(es), post address - will only be collected for the purposes of inviting me for, and organising, the CoP meetings, and will not be used for other purposes or transmitted to any third parties outside the B-WaterSmart Project.		

	YES	NO
I understand that my opinions and informations conveyed during the meetings may be used and directly quoted in conference communications, scientific publications, policy briefs and reports, but will be anonymised previously, ensuring the principles of confidentiality and privacy.		
I understand that in any case where there might be the need to quote my opinions and attribute them to my personal name I will be informed first and asked specific and written permission for that purpose (be it a journal article, Project newsletter, conference communication or any other purpose).		
I understand that any researcher will only be able to access and utilise my data and information if they agree to the confidentiality and privacy requirements stated above.		
I agree that my data will be securely stored on the Project online repository – Nextcloud – and on public open access repositories once anonymised, so they can be used for future reference, communication, and publications about water management issues.		
I agree to concede any author rights that I might retain, in relation to the information conveyed during the CoP meetings, for purposes of citation in the publications and communications of the B-WaterSmart Project.		

Full name: _____

Place and date: _____

Signature: _____

Informed consent form

Collection of video image and sound

Video, photo and sound collected during this meeting will only be used by the B-WaterSmart team and in accordance with EU GDPR, for the purposes of transcribing and analysing the information conveyed by participants, in support of the research publications and reports mentioned above.

All personal data will be anonymised previous to their analysis, and will not be shared with third parties, being used only for the purposes of this Project, as mentioned in the information sheet. All data will be stored in devices protected by password and in the Project online repository Nextcloud (restrict access), and will only be accessed by the B-WaterSmart team members. Short video clips or photos might be used for communicating the activities of the Project on its website or newsletter, in which case specific permission will be requested from the CoP participants who appear on the video/audio recordings.

	YES	NO
I give my permission for the collection of audio recordings during this meeting		
I give my permission for the collection of video images during this meeting		
I give my permission for the collection of photos during this meeting		
I authorise that sound is used for the purposes stated above		
I authorise that images are used for the purposes stated above		
I understand that I can request that my images, video or sound be deleted at any time		

Full name: _____

Place and date: _____

Signature: _____

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